

ExCASES Mission

Who decides for nature?

Embedding deliberative democracy in biodiversity renewal

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At a glance

In 2022, three conservation charities came together to run the first ever UK citizens' assembly on nature. As part of this unique and groundbreaking collaboration, the National Trust, Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB) and the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF-UK) assembled 103 members of the UK public from all walks of life to create an action plan for nature, 'for the people, by the people'. Their vision was expressed in 26 ambitious 'Calls to Action' targeting government, charities, businesses, individuals and communities.¹

Who decides for nature presents the findings of an [ExCASES 'mission'](#) (rapid research project), which took a close-up look at the challenges, successes, lessons and deliberative legacy of the People's Plan for Nature process, 'the UK's largest ever public conversation about the future of nature'.²

In keeping with the [ExCASES](#) agile and co-design model of working, the project employed an iterative process, using interviews and a workshop to draw on the expertise of 34 participants from inside – and outside – the People's Plan for Nature process and nature sector. These participants included: the People's Plan commissioning team and delivery partners, Assembly members, speakers and on-call experts; democracy experts and practitioners; legal, policy and inclusion specialists; national and local government officials; conservation sector representatives (including youth leaders); business and farming interests; and community engagement and participation practitioners.

Using a newly launched evaluation framework, developed by the *Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies (KNOCA)*,³ the study evaluates the **impacts** of the People's Plan for Nature, and offers **lessons** from the process for policymakers, practitioners and academics wanting to understand and integrate more inclusive and effective decision-making processes to bring positive outcomes for people and biodiversity renewal. Drawing on the expertise of the mission's diverse participants, a spotlight is cast on innovative examples and **recommendations** are provided for how the sector can apply these lessons to pull together as a more **holistic, deliberative democratic system** to benefit people and nature.

Key findings

- 1** The People's Plan for Nature created a powerful public mandate for nature action, showing there is an appetite and shared urgency among a representative cross-section of the population for a progressive environmental agenda.
- 2** The process has raised the salience of pro-nature policy and pushed the boundaries of what ambitious action for nature could look like by proposing radical new pathways, such as calling for: access to nature as a human right, legal rights for future generations, a permanent Assembly for Nature, and a Director for Nature on every company board.
- 3** It has paved the way for more joined-up policies and cross-sectoral action for nature restoration, and accelerated a shift in attitudes about the value of citizens' assemblies and deliberative democracy more widely.
- 4** Deliberative activities should not be seen as one-off, democratically 'curated' events, but opportunities to embed equity and inclusion – and promote environmental justice – in wider governance structures.
- 5** There is an urgent need for the nature sector to pull together as a holistic deliberative system, promoting a 'people and nature' approach in partnership with the public sector, businesses, communities and individuals.
- 6** Leaders and funders should implement longer project horizons and funding cycles to demonstrate their commitment to transformative social and environmental change.

Summary of lessons and recommendations

Embedding deliberative democracy in the nature sector

Lessons from the People's Plan for Nature	Recommendations for building a holistic deliberative system for nature
1 Use an impact strategy and theory of change	1 Take a holistic 'systems' approach to restoring nature
2 Clearly communicate objectives and limitations	2 Acknowledge and navigate disagreement and conflict
3 Engage in co-design to share the journey	3 Place communities at the heart of decision-making
4 Acknowledge the role of politics and power	4 Cultivate a mindset of power <i>with</i> citizens
5 Consider equality, diversity and inclusion at every stage	5 Centre marginalised and unheard voices
6 Demonstrate the integrity and value of the process	6 Engage publics and stakeholders in hybrid deliberative processes
7 Highlight the importance of leadership buy-in	7 Lead and collaborate across the nature sector – and beyond
8 Connect deliberative and representative democracy	8 Build an evidence base of public engagement and deliberative initiatives
9 Co-deliver and collaborate to maximise reach	9 Take a 'people and nature' approach
10 Take a cross-sectoral approach	10 Recognise transformative change demands commitment, resources and time

RENEW is a five-year partnership programme to develop solutions to one of the major environmental challenges for humankind: the renewal of biodiversity.

We are in a biodiversity crisis. A million species of plants and animals are threatened with global extinction, and wildlife populations across much of the planet have been dramatically reduced. This is of profound concern because biodiversity underpins human existence. RENEW is working, with a sense of urgency, to reshape understanding and action on biodiversity renewal across scales, creating knowledge, and influencing national institutions, communities and individuals. Our focus is on a 'people-in-nature' approach, reflecting the two-way, dynamic relations between people and nature and the need to develop a relational approach to renew our life-support systems.

Funded by the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), the programme is a collaboration between the University of Exeter and the National Trust, and has been co-designed and developed with over 30 partners from a diverse range of sectors.

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List of participating organisations

All the Elements, Citizens from the People's Assembly for Nature, Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs (Defra), Environment Agency, Green Party, Involve, Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies (KNOCA), Lawyers for Nature, London School of Economics, iswe Foundation, National Farmers' Union, National Trust, Natural England, New Citizenship Project, Plymouth City Council, Raven Network, Right to Roam, Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB), Sortition Foundation, UK Youth for Nature, University of Exeter, Lancaster University, University of Westminster, Wildlife and Countryside Link, The Wildlife Trusts, World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) - UK.

Who decides for nature?

Embedding deliberative democracy in biodiversity renewal

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Executive summary

0. Executive summary

// Because the nature crisis affects everyone, everyone should have a say in how we solve it.”

The People’s Plan for Nature²

Why we need to rethink who decides for nature

The UK is one of the most nature-depleted countries in the world. The 2023 State of Nature report explains that almost a fifth of wildlife has been lost since the 1970s due to land use and climate change, and that the conservation knowledge required to reverse these declines is well established but now needs to be deployed urgently and at scale.⁴

But how can this be done in practice? It has become increasingly evident that environmental decline is fundamentally a social problem. Yet representative democracy is facing a crisis of trust, legitimacy and effectiveness in the UK and across the globe. Important societal (and non-human) voices are routinely marginalised or absent from decision-making processes, and ordinary people are increasingly disaffected by politics and the politicians who claim to represent them.⁵ Furthermore, those suffering the consequences of environmental degradation are often not the ones making the decisions.

In response to these concerns, a new and more optimistic wave of participatory decision-making has swept across (mostly) wealthy nations, centred on the concept of deliberative democracy. This is the idea(l) that to be legitimate and effective, decision-making needs to be more equal and inclusive.⁶ Notable recent national processes in the climate-nature space have been the UK Climate Assembly (2020), the Irish Children and Young People’s Assembly on Biodiversity Loss (2022), the Welsh Nature and Us Citizens’ Assembly (2023), and the ongoing citizen workshops as part of the UK’s national Food Conversation. These deliberative initiatives have generally been driven by governments in response to the climate emergency (or specific constitutional concerns) and have taken the form of citizens’ assemblies: spaces for representative groups of citizens to come together in a facilitated process, to collectively learn, communicate and decide on matters of common concern.⁷

Despite their early promise, however, the impacts and effectiveness of such processes have been unclear or disappointing, partly because their outputs have been thrown back into the same political context from which they were born. Their recommendations are rarely woven into political agendas, enshrined in public policy or championed by society (with some notable exceptions).⁸ Understanding whether and why this is the case is essential for improving the design, desirability and impacts of future processes.

In 2022, three conservation charities launched a deliberative process of their own. The People’s Plan for Nature was commissioned by the National Trust, RSPB, and WWF as the first national conversation about nature, culminating in a ground-breaking citizens’ assembly, the first of its kind convened by a coalition of environmental organisations.

This [ExCASES study](#) takes a closer look at the impacts and lessons from the process. It evaluates its outcomes to help inform future initiatives and provides recommendations for embedding deliberative democracy in the nature sector (and beyond) to build on its legacy.

// Getting a better model of citizen engagement and deliberative democracy going is such an exciting opportunity, and the People's Plan for Nature process has opened that door well."

Richard Benwell, *CEO, Wildlife and Countryside Link*

Navigate directly to the corresponding sections in the report by clicking on the [hyperlinks](#).

- 1 In the [public arena](#), the People's Plan for Nature has created a powerful mandate for nature action by demonstrating that there is an appetite and shared urgency among a representative cross-section of the population for a progressive environmental agenda.**
 - It has paved the way for more ambitious and joined-up nature policy (e.g., land management, Environment Improvement Plan), and had some direct impacts (i.e., the sand eel fishing ban).
 - The language of the People's Plan for Nature, and interest in citizens' assemblies, has been echoed by policymakers, including in the 2025 Labour and Liberal Democrat party manifestos and subsequent discussions around public access to nature.
- 2 Within [society](#), the process has been 'transformative' and capacity-building for participants.**
 - An overwhelming majority of those involved found the experience rewarding, empowering and even life-changing, with many subsequently seeing themselves as changemakers and pioneers of the People's Plan for Nature and deliberative democracy.
 - The process has promoted civic education and capacity-building for Assembly members, commissioners, instigating charities, delivery partners, businesses and communities involved in follow-up programmes.
 - Assembly participants have demonstrated pro-environment behavioural change in their roles as citizens, investors, organisational members, employees/ers and consumers.
 - Follow-up programmes have led to greater cross-sectoral collaboration between the commissioning conservation charities, businesses, local communities and citizens.
 - The process has inspired new local, national and international deliberative initiatives, inside and outside the conservation sector, including those run by civil society organisations.
- 3 The People's Plan for Nature has planted seeds for potential [systems-level change](#).**
 - The process has provided validation for deliberative democracy as a concept and practice among influential institutions (large conservation charities, senior policymakers) and citizens.
 - It has pushed the boundaries of what ambitious action for nature might look like by proposing radical pathways, such as demanding access to nature as a human right, calling for a permanent Assembly for Nature, and introducing ideas relating to the rights of nature and future generations.
 - However, the extent of take-up will ultimately depend on the prevailing political climate, as the outputs of the People's Plan are fed back into the political and socio-economic systems from which they emerged.

Lessons and recommendations for embedding deliberative democracy

To inspire ambitious, collective pathways forward, we present ten lessons from the People's Plan for Nature process, which are loosely paired with ten recommendations drawn from this study.

1

Lesson: Use an impact strategy and theory of change

The People's Plan for Nature showed a high level of ambition in aiming for 'systems-level' change. It gave citizens a broad remit to shape the agenda, but this made the Plan challenging to implement. An explicit theory of change and impact strategy could have created clearer pathways to implement Calls to Action.

Recommendation: Take a holistic 'systems' approach to restoring nature

Organisations interested in restoring nature need to give more active consideration to how deliberative campaigns and democratic aspirations align with internal governance structures (and connect to external systems).

2

Lesson: Clearly communicate objectives and limitations

Deliberative initiatives provide opportunities for constructive communication and collaboration between people from different backgrounds on a range of complex issues. However, there is a need to be clear about objectives and parameters, roles and responsibilities. Some participants felt they were brought into the process too late or that funds could have been better spent elsewhere.

Recommendation: Acknowledge and navigate disagreement and conflict

Deliberative fora can be valuable for creating space and time to promote understanding of contentious topics (e.g., challenging historical legacies), and support navigating conflict and trade-offs. To be effective, however, deliberative approaches need to be coupled with an appetite for change from those in positions of authority.

3

Lesson: Engage in co-design to share the journey

A shared sense of purpose and stake in the implementation process is more likely to occur if you bring those you wish to engage, empower or influence into the process as early as possible and sustain their engagement throughout the process.

Recommendation: Place communities at the heart of decision-making

Maintaining a sense of meaning for people in places undergoing change is important. How people's stories and sense of place are layered onto the histories and cultures of their communities and landscapes will ultimately define whether and how they engage with nature. Listening to the needs of communities and putting them at the heart of decision-making will be key to reaching under-served communities and delivering equitable and inclusive nature restoration outcomes.

4

Lesson: Acknowledge the role of politics and power

Pervading all these lessons is the need to consider the concept of power. This is a useful framing for unlocking how longer-term social transformation might occur. Deliberative processes need to move beyond focusing on technical information and instead better incorporate politics, trade-offs, and alternative pathways to bringing about social change.

Recommendation: Cultivate a mindset of power with people

There is a need to 'normalise' citizens' voices being taken seriously in decision-making. More explicit attention needs to be given to power literacy and the ways organisations involved in nature restoration can make decisions 'with' rather than 'for' citizens. This also requires a shift from a transactional, campaigning mindset to a participation and empowerment approach.

5

Lesson: Consider equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI) at every stage

Whilst citizens' assemblies present a valuable and effective opportunity to 'do EDI better', they are not a panacea for achieving EDI, and even the best-designed deliberative spaces can be exclusionary. It is important that marginalised voices are incorporated on their own terms throughout the process.

Recommendation: Centre marginalised and unheard voices

Environmental justice calls for the meaningful inclusion of all people in environmental governance, ensuring negative impacts do not fall disproportionately on marginalised groups, future generations or nature itself. Conservation efforts need to go beyond 'formal' inclusion and make use of innovative methods to represent the rights of nature and future generations (such as guardianship and 'nature on the board'), and provide safe spaces for marginalised voices to build solidarity, empowerment and political efficacy (such as 'enclave' or affinity deliberations).*

6

Lesson: Demonstrate the integrity and value of the process

Beyond having the necessary firewalls in place to preserve the credibility of deliberative processes (e.g., an independent advisory board, professional delivery partners, following best practice), it is important to have a flexible and adaptive agenda, with provision for citizens/publics to request additional speakers or supplementary information. Careful consideration needs to be given to whether/how viewpoints that are considered political or 'extreme' are brought into the process (by including them, there may be claims of bias; without them, it may be difficult to bring about system change).

Recommendation: Engage publics and stakeholders in hybrid deliberative processes

There remains work to be done in raising public consciousness about the value and legitimacy of deliberative approaches, which would help to improve the diversity of those willing to participate and further legitimise such processes. Consideration should be given to how a range of formal and informal participatory and deliberative processes can be used to incorporate citizens/publics and stakeholders with decision-makers in different ways to enhance the 'deliberative function' of the nature governance system. They can be seen as a menu of bespoke methods to embed deliberative democracy, which can be applied across a range of sectors, contexts and time frames.

7

Lesson: Highlight the importance of leadership buy-in

The level of impact a deliberative event has will partly be a function of how much institutional buy-in there is from leadership, including within the commissioning organisations; this applies as much to charity-run processes as to government-led ones. Building coalitions of trust takes time and care. Without the goodwill of those in leadership roles and other strategic allies committing resources and support to the process as it unfolds, it is unlikely to have legacy.

Recommendation: Lead and collaborate across the sector - and beyond

The need for leadership and commitment across conservation organisations to bring about a more collaborative and deliberative approach to biodiversity renewal was voiced by many participants in this study. Alongside strategic direction, dedicated resources and training were mentioned as being necessary to manage sustainable partnerships, and translate lessons from deliberative and participatory processes into norms, institutions and practices.

*'Enclave' deliberation or affinity groups refer to provision of spaces for marginalised groups to deliberate separately or at different stages in a forum or process.⁹

8

Lesson: Connect deliberative and representative democracy

Finding ways to integrate deliberative events with representative democracy (public policy) can be particularly challenging for processes coming from outside the public sector, which may lack visibility and perceived legitimacy from key public actors. Bringing public policymakers close to deliberative processes can be valuable in demonstrating their value and legitimacy. At the same time, processes held outside the public sector may also be seen as being more credible by some publics, and an alternative route for building individual and societal efficacy.

Recommendation: Build an evidence base of public engagement and deliberative initiatives

Organisations engaged in nature conservation should establish an evidence base for mapping and evaluating the prevalence, impacts, and outcomes of participatory and deliberative processes to help build a better understanding of where and how they work best, and how such initiatives can be integrated into responsive environmental governance systems.

9

Lesson: Co-deliver and collaborate to maximise reach

The nature sector can be a territorial space. There is an urgent need for organisations working within it to come together in a way that plays to their strengths rather than operating as fragmented units.

Recommendation: Take a 'people and nature' approach

Although there has been a shift in framing of conservation thinking towards a 'people and nature' approach (highlighting ecosystem resilience and sociological systems in addition to species- and habitat-centred approaches), there remains a legacy of people being seen as the problem rather than integral to the solution. The historical dominance of natural science perspectives in conservation needs to be counterbalanced by greater social science literacy and attention to environmental justice perspectives.

10

Lesson: Take a cross-sectoral approach

It is important to see not only the conservation sector, but decision-making in all sectors, as playing a critical role in embedding deliberative democracy in nature renewal. Incorporating stakeholders from outside the conservation sector can be as impactful as collaborating with those within it.

Recommendation: Recognise transformative change demands commitment, resources and time

To effectively evaluate the impacts of deliberative processes, there is a need to continue monitoring their reach and significance over time and capture their long-term and unanticipated consequences. Leaders and funders need to be aware that longer-term commitment and funding horizons are required to deliver the transformative societal change necessary to tackle the nature and climate crises.

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Introduction

1. Introduction

Mission parameters and purpose

ExCASES is part of the [RENEW](#) project, a Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)-funded partnership between the University of Exeter and the National Trust, which takes a 'people-in-nature' approach towards the challenges of biodiversity renewal. The role of ExCASES is to undertake agile projects – which we term 'missions' – on pressing biodiversity renewal problems.

ExCASES missions provide short, intense periods of focus on issues that have been communicated as priorities for RENEW partner organisations and external stakeholders. The ExCASES team work collaboratively with people across different sectors and disciplines, co-designing research and participatory processes to generate empowering outcomes for people and the environment. This mission explored the impacts of the People's Plan for Nature (which we also refer to as the 'People's Plan'), and offers lessons from the process for policymakers, practitioners and academics wanting to understand and integrate more inclusive and effective decision-making for people and nature. It provides recommendations for how the sector can apply these lessons and operate as a more holistic, deliberative democratic system.

In keeping with the ExCASES agile and co-design model of working, expertise was drawn from a diverse range of stakeholders from the embryonic stages of the project, to help develop the mission's focus and scope. The analysis was based on interviews and a workshop, involving 34 participants in total, including: the core commissioning team, Assembly for Nature members (citizens), speakers and on-call experts; representatives from the conservation and farming sectors; democracy experts; legal, policy and inclusion specialists; national and local government officials; and community engagement and participation practitioners. Participants were invited to reflect on their experiences with the process, and asked to consider how the nature sector could move forward together more effectively to build on the People's Plan's deliberative legacy.

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What is biodiversity?
What is nature?
Why does it matter?

1.1 Why we need to rethink who decides for nature

The UK is now one of the most nature-depleted countries on Earth,⁴ and decisions being made now will be critical to reversing the alarming rates of biodiversity loss we are seeing. There is an increasing awareness that without incorporating a broader range of voices and interests in decision-making, we are unlikely to unlock the transformative pathways necessary to address these defining, complex and 'wicked' problems of our time.^{8,10}

It is also increasingly clear that people's feelings of connection with nature are waning. The UK's level of 'nature connection' was 16th lowest in a study across 18 high-income countries,¹¹ and humanity's impacts and reliance on the rest of the natural world are often overlooked or lost in everyday choices.¹² Almost half of the people responding to the People and Nature survey in England were 'unaware' of the threat to biodiversity or unconcerned about it.¹³ In the words of David Attenborough, 'No-one will protect what they don't care about, and no-one will care about what they have never experienced.'

Much current decision-making about nature – and the interests consciously or subconsciously informing these processes – are locked into what are known as 'structural' patterns, meaning that while people's behaviours, practices, cultures and institutions are malleable, they are shaped and regulated by the social, economic and political systems already in place. These systems have often been historically determined by those who hold power and influence (e.g., owners or managers of land and assets), and whose interests, knowledge and needs have been prioritised over those of others. This has arguably led to the marginalisation of other important societal voices, and limited representation of the wider natural world.

Nature has traditionally sat at the periphery of concerns of policymakers, business leaders and publics.^{4,14} Recent research shows that policymakers and civil servants are increasingly detached from the lives and experiences of everyday citizens. By their own admission, they are often informed by 'a small pool of the same people or organisations who may themselves be far from the actual individuals on the ground, and usually not those that are implementing the policy or feeling the impact of it.'⁵ Not only do they report feeling disempowered to pioneer innovative solutions, but the instability of day-to-day politics serves to hamper long-term thinking.⁵

Trust and confidence in the UK's system of government, and in politicians and policymakers, is also at an all-time low.¹⁵ This distrust of policymakers and communicators is said to be undermining both public demand and collective capacity to address environmental sustainability challenges, not least because a sizable minority do not believe these problems (e.g., climate change) exist in the first place.^{16,17} Rebuilding confidence is important because trust in institutions, scientists and environmental groups correlates positively with pro-environmental behaviours.^{18,19}

The environmental sector faces significant challenges of its own related to diversity and representation; it is one of the least ethnically diverse of all professions, second only to farming.²⁰ Participation and leadership, as well as perspectives on outdoor spaces, environmental education and human-nature relationships often fail to reflect the demographics, perspectives and experiences of broader society.^{21–23} Although this issue is widely acknowledged, there is still a need improve ethnic diversity and inclusivity across equity and empowerment metrics, such as developing targets and building capacity for people of colour to take on more senior and leadership roles^{24–26}.

The People's Plan for Nature

In response to many of these problems, a recent wave of 'deliberative' processes has taken place globally to experiment with more inclusive and participatory styles of democratic governance. This has built on the idea that new spaces and methods are needed to bring together institutions, agencies, activists and citizens to deliberate on social issues.²⁷ The motivation has been to improve legitimacy and equality by including citizens in making the decisions that affect them. These may be informal grassroots networks, longer-term collaborative dialogues/councils or highly structured deliberative processes, such as citizens' assemblies, juries and panels.²⁷⁻²⁹

This research focuses on a particular example of deliberative governance: a citizens' assembly known as the People's Plan. Between October 2022 and March 2023, three environmental NGOs (eNGOs) – the National Trust, Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB), and World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) UK – decided to embark on a citizens' assembly of their own, launching the People's Plan for Nature: 'the UK's largest ever [National Conversation](#) about the future of nature,' to 'build a groundswell of engagement and awareness,' based on what communities were already doing.²

This culminated in the [People's Assembly for Nature](#), where 103 citizens from 'all walks of life' were chosen via a democratic lottery to represent the UK population in a structured, deliberative process to explore how best to address the nature crisis.²

1.2 Research rationale

// If citizens' assemblies are intended to open possibilities for systemic transformations...there is a need to learn from past experiences where this has either taken place or not, and why."

Mellier and Capstick, 2022³⁰

The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) has tracked over [750 representative deliberative processes](#) globally since 1979.³¹ A third of those running between 2021-3 related to the green agenda,³² and more than 200 climate assemblies have been held in Europe alone.³³ Notable recent processes in the climate-nature space have been the UK Climate Assembly (2020), the Irish Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss (2022), the Welsh Nature and Us Citizens' Assembly (2023), and the ongoing citizen workshops as part of the UK's national [Food Conversation](#).

Such fora have been promoted as innovative ways to 'democratise' decision-making by: creating more legitimate, popular mandates for change; increasing participation and representation in decision-making; enhancing civic education; and generating novel and effective solutions.³⁴ In doing so, it is argued, they hold the promise of addressing some of the deficits of representative democracy by improving the quality, legitimacy and feasibility of environmental outcomes.³⁵ What is less clear is how legitimate, credible and useful they are for those involved, and whether they actually represent a fairer and more effective way of making decisions.³⁶ There are also questions as to whether these models maintain the same biases as existing ways of doing things, and how inclusive deliberative democracy is in reality for marginalised groups, both in terms of the composition of deliberative bodies, as well as more, 'subtle forms of exclusion that suppress or discount historically marginalised groups'.³⁷ Further, there is limited evidence for the ability of citizens' assemblies to bring about systemic transformations, i.e., deep-seated changes to the underlying principles, goals and mandates that drive our motivations, practices and action for nature. Exploring these core issues were the focus of this mission.

1.3 Citizens' assemblies and deliberative democracy

// Democratic processes always begin with inclusion, since collective agendas and decisions are only 'democratic' to the degree that those affected by collective outcomes are empowered to influence them."

Beauvais, 2018⁶

The concept of deliberative democracy is important for biodiversity renewal because it paints a picture of an 'ideal' context for decision-making. As such, it can be understood as a process and an aspiration. To break down the term, democracy refers to the need for equality and inclusion (translated literally as 'rule by the people' from the Greek term).⁶ Deliberation refers to a two-way process of communication involving weighing and considering preferences, values, and interests on matters of shared concern.³⁸ This includes considerations about why people disagree. Both dimensions are relevant to decision-making about nature in light of ongoing perceptions (captured in several interviews conducted as part of this mission) that the sector has not always included or listened to the needs of local communities and publics.

Deliberative democracy can be seen as a helpful benchmark against which to judge how inclusive and equitable governance processes are. The perspective suggests decisions should be made in a context of mutual respect, recognition, reciprocity, and sufficient equality of status between members to ensure everyone has the power to influence outcomes.^{38,39}

These processes can take a range of formats, varying from being highly structured to more informal. **Citizens' assemblies**, such as the People's Plan, are an example of a very structured type of deliberative process. They fall into the category of a 'mini-public' because they have the following key characteristics: (a) participants are chosen at random by a democratic lottery (known as sortition) – so that in principle, every citizen has the same chance of being selected; and (b) the composition of the selected group is designed to broadly reflect the demographic characteristics of the wider population. They tend to follow a multi-stage process outlined in Figure 1, although in the case of the People's Plan, the pathway for disseminating recommendations was less clear, as discussed later.

FIGURE 1: STAGES IN A CITIZENS' ASSEMBLY PROCESS

SOURCE: *INSTITUTE FOR GOVERNMENT EXPLAINER* ⁴⁰

Volunteers participating in these processes can vary in number from around 12-30 in the case of juries and panels, to 50-150 for citizens' assemblies. Events typically take place in a facilitated space over a period of time, to exchange and critique information and ideas relevant to issues of common concern, and agree on collective pathways forward.

Being an ideal, the reality invariably falls short of these high standards. Some critics claim deliberative democracy doesn't necessarily provide an easier environment for marginalised groups to participate, given that the same biases and hierarchies of privilege still apply.⁴¹ Nevertheless, measured against the status quo, deliberative democracy does at least try to mitigate against some of the core weaknesses of our current model of representative democracy by promoting procedural formats that limit coercive power, for example, by choosing participants that are less overtly partisan/biased, using independent facilitators or holding deliberations in public.⁴²

In other words, we can't influence who meets politicians, bureaucrats or CEOs behind closed doors or know exactly what they have discussed or how this shapes decisions that affect us, but within deliberative-democratic fora, we can at least consciously try to ensure there is higher degree of transparency, greater diversity of representation, and a fairer chance that marginalised voices will be present and heard. By accommodating a wider range of voices, knowledge and lived experiences, as well as incorporating time for learning and exchange, deliberative democracy can also create more conducive conditions for participants to consider complex problems, longer-term horizons, conflicting interests, and difficult trade-offs.⁴³ Although everyone may not agree with the outcomes, there may be greater trust in the process. This may lead to a sense of empowerment for those taking part, greater acceptability of outputs from the wider population, and heightened confidence among decision-makers to implement a progressive agenda if it is backed by a popular mandate.

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1.4 Aims and objectives

Aim

This mission aimed to explore how insights from the People's Plan and other innovative participatory processes can be used to better integrate deliberative democratic cultures and practices within the environment and nature sectors.

Objectives

Who decides for Nature:

- 1) Explores the influence and impacts of the People's Plan to date;
- 2) Shares lessons from the People's Plan, and experiences from other participatory initiatives, to help amplify learning and apply deliberative democracy across the initiating organisations, the RENEW programme, and the sector more broadly;
- 3) Identifies how we can use learning from the People's Plan to improve participation within organisations involved in biodiversity renewal to embed or 'systematise' deliberative democracy within their systems and culture.

1.5 Methodology

A critical case study approach was used to enable an in-depth study, with the aim of drawing lessons from the People's Plan for future deliberative processes.⁴⁴ The People's Plan was seen as a 'critical' case due to its strategic importance as one of the first multi-eNGO-commissioned national citizens' assemblies of its kind in the nature sector.⁴⁵ This approach allowed 'how' and 'why' questions to be asked to enrich our understanding of citizens' assemblies more generally, and constructively contribute to the development of deliberative practices and institutional innovation to support transformative social change for biodiversity restoration.⁴⁶

The value of taking a systems approach to deliberative democracy

“ A system here means a set of distinguishable, differentiated, but to some degree interdependent parts, often with distributed functions and a division of labour, connected in such a way as to form a complex whole.”

Mansbridge et al., 2012⁴⁷

We investigated lessons from the People's Plan by taking a systemic approach to deliberative democracy.^{39,47} This involved seeing the process as just one (small) part of a broader system of environmental governance, with units “interacting together to produce a healthy deliberative system.”^{6,47} It had the advantage of enabling us to analyse how the process functioned within a constellation of other actors and institutions, and to consider the strengths and weaknesses of different parts of the system as a whole (and any gaps or biases it might have).⁴⁷ The idea of 'embedding' deliberative democracy refers to exploring how the values and goals associated with deliberative democracy have been applied to wider practices, processes and systems for nature restoration.

Research methods

A flexible and iterative, mixed-method approach was used and adapted over the course of the project in response to inputs from **34 participants**. This included:

- **Documentary analysis**, i.e., examining official organisational responses, progress reports, evaluations, and media outputs associated with the People's Plan to inform and contextualise findings. An early literature review engaged with relevant theories and concepts, drawing on the advice and expertise of the participants involved in early co-design, to shape the direction and parameters of the study.
- **28 interviews** were conducted (April-August 2024) with: members of the People's Plan's commissioning and delivery teams; Assembly citizens; speakers and on-call experts from the Assembly; representatives from the nature and environment sector; academics specialising in participatory and deliberative processes; experts in law, policy, and inclusion; representatives from national and local governments; and community engagement practitioners. Interviews were recorded and transcribed. Specific attention was given to understanding the extent to which the process had served or impacted marginalised and under-represented communities, in keeping with guidance published by the [Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies](#), whose *Impact Evaluation Framework for Climate Assemblies* is used in this study (see below).³ The majority of interviews took place prior to the workshop, with several more occurring afterwards to gather a wider range of viewpoints. Information from interviews underpins the analysis and provides the basis for the arguments made. Where permission was granted, quotes are included (with the level of attribution left to the discretion of the interviewee).
- A **participatory workshop** was held online in July 2024 with 16 participants, including 10 interviewees and six additional members, who were invited due to their specific expertise in: the People's Plan process, EDI, citizens' assemblies, and the use of deliberative democracy in a variety of settings (including government, business and civil society sectors). Participants were invited to share their experiences and learning from the People's Plan, and draw on other innovative participatory processes, to collaboratively explore lessons from the People's Plan, and give recommendations for how to 'embed' deliberative democracy in nature governance.
- **Participant observation** was employed at the People's Plan's one-year impact event, *Together for Nature*, held in Manchester in April 2024. This provided an opportunity for informal conversations with the commissioning organisations, Assembly members, and community groups who had received funding from follow-on projects (i.e., *Nature Neighbourhoods and the Save Our Wild Isles Community Fund*). Attending the launch of New Citizenship Project's RAPID Democracy report (May 2023) also provided useful background about the philosophy underpinning the People's Plan, and how it has been applied elsewhere.
- An **impact evaluation** was conducted using the recently launched *Impact Evaluation Framework for Climate Assemblies*, developed for the Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies (KNOCA).³ KNOCA is a European-based network, which draws on the expertise of over 600 members from 39 countries to improve the design, quality and understanding of citizens' assemblies on climate change and (increasingly also) the environment.

These methods were **triangulated** (i.e. cross-referenced), to provide a more comprehensive, valid and credible picture, mindful to incorporate insights from those both inside and outside the process to ensure critical voices, and those who may have had a different frame of reference for judging the 'success' of the process, were included (e.g., it was evident that different participants placed different emphases on policy outcomes, inclusion/EDI, community engagement, and social change).

Transcripts from interviews and the workshop were coded, and thematic analysis was conducted to draw out key areas of interest, consensus and divergence. A further round of triangulation took place in early 2025 to seek approval for citations (where participants had requested this), as well as to ask for updates on impacts, and validation for sections of text or diagrams. Ethical approval was given to this study by the Faculty of Environment, Science and Economy at the University of Exeter (ID 6147707).

1.6 The People's Plan for Nature

// Created for the people, by the people of the UK – a vision for the future of nature, and the actions we must all take to protect and renew it.”

The People's Plan for Nature¹

Origins of the People's Plan for Nature

The People's Plan began as a collaboration between the RSPB and WWF, and later the National Trust, to co-create a public mobilisation campaign around the BBC television production, *Wild Isles*. This was the first documentary series presented by David Attenborough about nature in Britain.

Members of the commissioning team had been inspired by the [UK's Climate Assembly in 2020](#) and [Jersey's 2021 Citizens' Assembly on Climate Change](#), and *Wild Isles* was seen as a fresh opportunity for the charities to engage members of the public who were not necessarily their supporters, at a time when eNGO influence on politics had been on the wane, and trust in politics was low. The concluding [episode](#) in the *Wild Isles* series was co-commissioned by the three eNGOs to showcase their nature renewal activities and inspire the public to join their [Save Our Wild Isles](#) campaign.

Defining objectives: 'RAPID' democracy

The context within which the People's Plan evolved was already unique compared with many other citizens' assembly processes: it was instigated by three charities (as opposed to a public authority); it was inspired by and embedded within a public media campaign; and it was supported from the outset by a strategic framework known as '[RAPID Democracy](#)'. The latter was a process developed by the [New Citizenship Project](#) to help restore trust and legitimacy between publics and decision-makers across the state, business and charity sectors, centred around the view that organisations need to see people less as 'subjects' and 'consumers', and more as 'citizens'.^{48,49} It was therefore seen as the rolling out of a process to help democratise decisions about nature and a means of starting a conversation with these groups. Underpinning this perspective, was the imperative for public authorities, companies and organisations to make decisions *with* rather than *for* citizens across all five key stages of the decision-making cycle, i.e., Input, Recommend, Agree, Decide, and Perform (deliver the plan) (see Figure 2).⁴⁹

The People's Plan process was designed to represent the first two of these five phases (Input and Recommend), centred around the question of what should be done to protect and restore nature in the UK.

FIGURE 2: THE NEW CITIZENSHIP PROJECT'S RAPID DEMOCRACY MODEL APPLIED TO THE PEOPLE'S PLAN FOR NATURE
SOURCE: NEW CITIZENSHIP PROJECT⁴⁹

The **National Conversation** provided Input to the Assembly via a four-week, creative visioning exercise about the future of nature, which invited members of the public to submit ideas and inspiration for how to protect nature and wildlife, online and in person at art centres, schools, football clubs and National Trust properties.

The **People's Assembly for Nature** that followed selected 103 members of the public via a democratic lottery, which was run by the [Sortition Foundation](#) to reflect the demographic profile of the UK population (in terms of age, gender, ethnicity, geography, urban-rural socioeconomic status, and agreement with the statement, 'I feel part of nature').² The Assembly were given the opportunity to creatively engage with the 30,000 contributions received in the National Conversation, and invited to feed these perspectives into the citizens' assembly process, which represented the Recommend phase. The process ran over four weekends between November 2022 and February 2023.

Providing expert input: balancing different opinions

// You need to answer the case that you're not just pushing forward the existing agenda of an organisation. One of the main reasons behind deliberation is to make sure you hear from everybody, not only people who already have a voice in the process."

Professor Rebecca Willis

To counter potential claims of bias, and in keeping with best practice for running assemblies, an independent, 18-member [Advisory Group](#) was appointed (with two academic leads), to provide accountability, advice, scrutiny, and to, 'ensure that Assembly members were presented with factually accurate, comprehensive, balanced and unbiased information.'² They were chosen for their expertise and to be 'representative of a broad range of ideological standpoints, representing different parts of society, including business, government representatives, academia, NGOs and civil society groups.'

To offer a further firewall against potential claims of bias, independent delivery partners were recruited to support the process. [Involve](#) were hired to deliver the citizens' assembly. As the process was led by eNGOs, it was felt there was a particular need to demonstrate impartiality and integrity, which was addressed by providing as much transparency as possible around governance, such as publishing the programme of activities, list of speakers, and recordings of expert presentations on the campaign's [website](#). As some of those involved reflected in interview, this required a genuine leap of faith from the commissioning organisations, and the project felt markedly different to others they had participated in.

// Whilst we knew it was part of a wider campaign, we didn't quite know what was going to come out of [the Assembly], so the process felt different as there needed to be a lot of trust in the...[outcomes]."

Member of the People's Plan's commissioning team

Deliberating for impact: 'whole-system change'

// The RAPID process can unlock stalemates between different system actors (such as governments, businesses and communities) and allow the whole system to move. Indeed, this project demonstrates how all parts of the system can step into the power they have."

The People's Plan for Nature²

Being integrated within a RAPID Democracy framework, the People's Assembly was designed to promote visionary, forward-thinking and 'whole-system change'.² The core output of the People's Plan process was 26 Calls to Action, spanning eight themes (see Figure 3). These were created on the final weekend, using an iterative, deliberative process where Assembly members nominated key topics of interest, which they refined into Calls for Action using their own words.

After the People's Assembly ended, members were encouraged to engage with e-petitions to lobby their MPs to implement the Plan. They were also offered support with their 'onward journey,' including media training, and a partnership with the [Groundwork](#) network, who provided capacity-building opportunities via local trusts working with communities and businesses. For those who signed up to the process, this involved regular meetings over six months, access to workshops and mentoring (see [Section 2.2.1](#) for more on Assembly members' experiences).

The People's Plan for Nature process

PHASE 1: NATIONAL CONVERSATION / 30 September – 30 October 2022

- An open call for ideas, stories, aspirations and experiences relating to nature in the UK
- 74 interactive installations at art centres, schools, football clubs, National Trust properties, and social media used to inspire the conversation
- 30,000 responses are collated and posted on the [People's Plan for Nature website](#)
- 45 commentaries and illustrations from this process are made available to the People's Assembly

PHASE 2: PEOPLE'S ASSEMBLY FOR NATURE / November 2022 – February 2023

- 18 members of Advisory Group ensure independent oversight over design and content
- 103 citizens selected at random to be representative of the UK public (with respect to age, education, geographical region, ethnicity and engagement with nature)
- 36 hours of deliberation take place over four weekends (two in-person, two online)
- 40 speakers present perspectives

26 CALLS TO ACTION ACROSS 8 THEMES / March 2023

- Targeting: national and local governments, charities and NGOs, businesses, individuals and communities

FIGURE 3: THE PEOPLE'S PLAN FOR NATURE PROCESS

Impacts of the People's Plan for Nature

2. Impacts of the People's Plan for Nature

To help explore the impacts of the People's Plan, the analysis draws on KNOCA's *Impact Evaluation Framework for Climate Assemblies*.³ This highlights a 'matrix' of impacts across two dimensions: area of impact, and type of impact (detailed in [Table 1](#)).

- **Area of impact** relates to where and for whom changes happen, i.e., (1) public actors (in the political arena), (2) non-state actors (in public, societal and business spheres), and (3) systems and structures (shifts in collective understandings and perspectives about how actors approach nature restoration).

- **Type of impact** refers to: (a) what is 'being done' (instrumental changes), (b) capacity-building (capacity and resources to get things done), and (c) concepts, goals and principles (how the problem is understood).

There are, of course, overlaps across these areas, but using this framework allows us to broadly locate where key impacts are concentrated. The analysis also comes with a health warning about time frames, tracing influence, and context. First, it's important to remember that this analysis represents a snapshot in time, and not the final word. While it is based on interviews and resources that have been made available for this research, further changes are likely to emerge over time – and some may not materialise until long after the event, so it's useful to consider the following as an 'evaluation in progress'. Second, impacts are often hard to pinpoint in terms of their cause and effect, so it's helpful to see citizens' assemblies as one of many possible influences, some of which may have a direct or indirect effect, and be mindful that contextual factors (such as the political climate) will play a key role.⁵⁰

AREA of impact ↓	TYPE of impact →		
	A. INSTRUMENTAL <i>What is being 'done'</i>	B. CAPACITY <i>Expertise and resources to act</i>	C. CONCEPTUAL <i>Ways of understanding action for nature</i>
1. PUBLIC SECTOR Impacts on government decision-making <i>Key actors: policymakers, politicians, parliamentarians, civil servants</i>	Changes to formal policy, strategy, legislation, laws, regulation and official guidance.	Changes in expertise and resources for action, including connecting deliberation and public engagement to policymaking.	Changes to understanding of action by state actors, including role of public engagement and perspectives.
2. SOCIAL/ CORPORATE Impacts on wider society and public discourse <i>Key actors: members of the public, media, businesses, and third-sector (e.g., charities, NGOs)</i>	Changes to behaviour by wider publics; changes to business, media or organisational policies and practices; changes in behaviour of assembly members.	Changes in expertise and resources for engaging in action by non-state actors, such as civil society initiatives to establish greater public contribution to action.	Changes to understanding of action by civil society, media and business organisations, including enhanced recognition of the importance of nature in practices, and role of public perspectives and engagement.
3. SYSTEMS AND STRUCTURES Impacts on underlying features of practices (including decision-making) that alter the goals or mandates that guide climate action	Changes to underlying governance system within which society addresses nature renewal (e.g., new incentive/tax systems, shifts in responsibilities).	Changes in organising principles or in expertise and resources available to tackle systemic nature of nature crisis.	Fundamental shifts in shared understandings and ideas about appropriate ways of acting for nature, and how this may relate to other societal challenges.

TABLE 1: EVALUATION FRAMEWORK FOR CITIZENS' ASSEMBLY IMPACTS

SOURCE: ADAPTED FROM KNOCA'S IMPACT EVALUATION FRAMEWORK FOR CLIMATE ASSEMBLIES³

2.1 Public sector impacts

// There has been positive momentum in the short term, but the campaigns needed a ‘longer runway’

National Trust, RSPB and WWF, *Internal impact evaluation, 2024*⁵¹

2.1.1 Effects on public policy and decision-making

Policy change is commonly considered to be the main target impact for citizens’ assemblies; yet this is an area where citizens’ assemblies often fail to deliver.⁵² It is perhaps unsurprising, therefore, that a citizens’ assembly run by three eNGOs, at a time when political attention was decidedly elsewhere (the assembly period included the death of Queen Elizabeth II and Liz Truss’s turbulent tenure as Prime Minister), had only a modest impact on policy, laws and regulation.

Shortly after the publication of the People’s Plan, there was a flurry of activity in the political sphere, largely driven by the advocacy efforts of the commissioning organisations, who worked hard to amplify the voices of Assembly members and lobby policymakers behind the scenes. For example, ‘People’s Champions’ (as Assembly members became known), were invited to attend a Westminster Abbey garden event and speak at a [roundtable](#) hosted by Peers for the Planet and the Environment All Party Parliamentary Group (APPG).⁵³ Nevertheless, interviewees in policy circles acknowledged that more traditional parliamentary representatives remained sceptical about the role of deliberative democracy and powers being taken away from elected representatives.

An internal progress report prepared by the commissioning organisations, which was undertaken a year after the People’s Plan went public, cited over 120 areas of change on nature policy relating to the People’s Plan’s recommendations.⁵⁴ However, causality between these developments and the People’s Plan was unclear, and many changes were primarily attributable to the overhaul of environmental and agricultural policy already underway across the UK.⁵⁴

As the General Election approached in July 2024, there was growing evidence that the People’s Plan was having ‘slow burning’ impact; the language used in the Labour and Liberal Democrat manifestos was notably more in-step with the People’s Plan, and several Labour advisors began publicly expressing an interest in using citizens’ assemblies.^{51,55,56} The National Green Party Spokesperson for Nature also explained in an interview for this project that the People’s Plan had reinforced the party’s mandate for a strong nature platform.

2.1 Public sector impacts continued

An internal evaluation of the umbrella *Save Our Wild Isles* (SOWI) campaign conducted shortly after the General Election concluded that the People's Plan and SOWI campaigns had impacted directly on public policy (e.g., being instrumental in bringing about the sand eels fishing ban), and claimed the rapport established between the commissioning organisations and policymakers through the campaign had laid the foundations for strong relationships with the new government when it came to power.⁵¹ It noted the People's Plan (and *Save Our Wild Isles*) had been used by senior policymakers to justify more ambitious policies for nature (securing further nature-positive action beyond the Environmental Improvement Plan) and to support public access to nature (in relation to the Regeneration and Levelling Up Bill).⁵¹

Extrapolating cause and effects, and tracing policy change back to a specific event, is fraught with methodological challenges and uncertainties, and time lags will be inevitable where significant changes are likely to occur. Nevertheless, there are strong indications that new pathways to change have gathered momentum due to the combined effects of the People's Plan, and a more favourable political context in the form of a more sympathetic government, not to mention relevant processes already in motion (e.g., implementation in England of Biodiversity Net Gain,⁵⁷ and the [Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures](#), meaning that nature objectives would now be an important factor in property development planning and global finance flows).

While the impact on formal politics, policy and institutions may have been limited so far, there is certainly evidence that the People's Plan has informed the public debate, legitimised the nature agenda, and galvanised coalitions to support a more progressive and proactive approach to nature policy, practice and implementation.

2.1 Public sector impacts continued

2.1.2 Building public sector capacity to act

// There have been a lot of countervailing forces against the nature agenda recently, and to be able to point to something that suggests a popular movement in the opposite direction, has been useful."

Richard Benwell, *CEO, Wildlife and Countryside Link*

Capacity-building impacts relate to changes in the skills, expertise and confidence state actors have to 'act for nature'.³ High profile examples of People's Plan impacts in this area include two Assembly members being elected as local councillors (a direct impact).

Perhaps most significantly, however, the People's Plan has served an important capacity-building function by producing a strong public mandate for nature action with comprehensive advisory recommendations, in the absence of this being provided elsewhere, which chimes with findings from other climate assemblies.⁵⁸

2.1.3 New ways of acting for nature by the public sector

Overlapping with findings in [Section 2.1.1](#), there is also evidence of state actors demonstrating shifts in their understanding and interest in nature policy and action over this period. Perhaps the most important conceptual breakthrough has been the People's Plan's contribution to the noticeable movement in attitudes towards the value of using citizens' assemblies and deliberative democracy, as voiced by Labour Ministers, MPs and advisors.^{55,56,59} Notably, Labour MP Clive Lewis has tabled a [Private Member's Bill](#) proposing a climate assembly to determine future water industry ownership.⁶⁰ Liberal Democrat MP, Liz Savage, also introduced the [Climate and Nature Bill 2024-5](#), a Private Member's Bill demanding that 'policy and action on the climate and nature crises is science-led and people-oriented'.¹²⁷ This had support from the Green Party, Plaid Cymru, SDLP, the Alliance Party and [Zero Hour](#), and called for a citizens' assembly to help develop a joined-up strategy for climate and nature; however, the Conservative spokesman specifically objected to the citizens' assembly element, saying, 'That is not how decisions are made in this country, and it is not how decisions should be made in this country.'¹²⁸ The bill did not progress after its sponsors came to an agreement with the government.¹²⁷

At the same time, members of the People Plan commissioning team have shared that they have been invited to consult with policymakers on future potential deliberative exercises involving citizens (e.g., at the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra), the Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, and Scotland's Futures Forum).

2.2 Changes in society: NGOs/charities, businesses and publics

2.2.1 New societal ways of acting for nature

// 103 individuals that are part of the process means 103 different stories. But for a lot of them, what you'll hear is about this transformation in agency, which is really exciting."

Member of the People's Plan commissioning team

The People's Plan for Nature, and the People's Assembly for Nature in particular, had powerful *personal* impacts on those involved. This personal transformation applied to the commissioning team, observers, and of course, Assembly members themselves, several of whom became 'People's Champions' and changemakers afterwards. Many cited the impact of seeing so many people from different walks of life coming together on (more) equal terms – to collectively formulate a coherent national agenda for nature – as being moving, inspirational, and sometimes, life changing. Even the minority of citizens who were sceptical at the start of the process (some of whom continued to be so at the end), admitted the experience had expanded their knowledge, changed their behaviours, and deepened their understanding of the urgent need to act for nature. Several of those interviewed, from ENGO staff to observers and citizens, used the word 'transformational' to describe their experiences of participating in the process, and were able to describe a chain reaction of changed perspectives, new behaviours and a revived sense of social purpose to act for nature, which has reverberated across their personal and professional lives, and extended into the social sphere more widely. Some of these experiences are recounted by People's Assembly members in Figure 4.

2.2 Changes in society: NGOs/charities, businesses and publics continued

// “The Assembly did shift my behaviour and attitudes significantly on some political things, like the way I will vote in the next election.

It’s also changed the activities I plan to work with as a CEO in infrastructure finance. I’m now trying to match organisations interested in ‘wilding’ with money.

I am also volunteering in the nearest park. I find it quite therapeutic. I enjoy meeting the other people. It’s manual work which I don’t normally do. I wouldn’t have done any of that before.”

David, CEO, Finance sector, People’s Assembly for Nature member

// Since the People’s Plan for Nature was published, I have continued to work alongside WWF, National Trust and RSPB to advocate the People’s Plan for Nature, including speaking in the House of Lords and to the National Trust magazine. I have made lifestyle changes, such as changing my diet, cutting out meat, fish and dairy. I rarely use the car now, and prefer to walk. It’s great for my physical and mental health; for any long or time-sensitive journeys, I now use public transport... I’ve also joined my local XR [Extinction Rebellion] group to do a bit of protest and try to keep behind them wherever I can.”

Peter, Carer, People’s Assembly for Nature member

// I’ve grown up in a city...not going out in nature apart from once a year on school trips. I loved those times.

Now I’m 50, I feel we haven’t got time. Since the Assembly, I’ve set up a Community Interest Company, and will be hosting a weekly radio show, ‘Nature Daze,’ where I’ll be involving other Assembly members, local businesses, environmentalists and farmers – asking what they are doing and what they intend to do to bring about *change!*

Children are our future. I want to get nature into schools, on the national curriculum. We now have a team of media students from the local college contributing to Nature Daze.

None of this would have happened without the Assembly. I’m forever a People’s Assembly for Nature member.”

Shantyl, Executive Creative Director for Radio Nation Coventry CIC, DJ, Mentor and Youth Advocate

FIGURE 4: IN THEIR OWN WORDS: EXAMPLES OF IMPACTS OF THE PEOPLE’S PLAN FOR NATURE ON ASSEMBLY MEMBERS
SOURCES: INTERVIEWS WITH MEMBERS OF THE PEOPLE’S ASSEMBLY FOR NATURE

2.2 Changes in society: NGOs/charities, businesses and publics continued

Psychological research highlights that there are multiple roles and pathways for an individual's behaviour to 'spillover' from one area of their life into others; and Assembly members have demonstrated particularly powerful behavioural changes or 'spillovers' in these roles as consumers, investors, organisational members, employees and citizens.⁶¹ Select examples include changes in their roles as:

- **Consumers** – switching away from meat and dairy, and using more public transport;
- **Investors** – using finance as a tool to support better investment choices for nature;
- **Organisational participants** – joining eNGOs (e.g., 70% became members of the commissioning organisations afterwards, 20-30 citizens continue to be ambassadors), becoming activists and campaigners (e.g., some joined Extinction Rebellion), engaging in green community work (such as volunteering with community gardens), and undertaking media outreach (15 People's Champions appeared in media features);
- **Employees** – setting up a Community Interest Company to run nature radio shows (see Figure 4), switching to activities promoting nature-friendly finance;
- **Citizens** – two have become local councillors, and some others have reported changing their voting intentions to support more environmentally-friendly candidates.⁵¹

Individual members of the commissioning team have also become institutional entrepreneurs within their own organisations, championing deliberative democracy and creating opportunities to amplify Assembly members' voices, by giving them prominence within their communications, campaigning and advocacy work, and inviting them to speak at events such as the Westminster Roundtable and *Save Our Wild Isles* business events.

At the organisational level, the three commissioning eNGOs have each published their own comprehensive responses to the People's Plan, explaining in detail how they intend or have already begun to integrate its recommendations into their work.⁶²⁻⁶⁴ Interesting examples are the RSPB trialling free access to their reserves for 16-24 year-olds, and all three eNGOs committing to use the language and framing around nature preferred by the People's Plan, with a shift in emphasis from nature 'protection' to 'renewal'. The National Trust's new strategy also includes 'ending unequal access to nature' by 2050 as one of its three core goals.⁶⁵

With respect to impacts on the conservation sector as a whole, Wildlife and Countryside Link made direct reference to the People's Plan in highlighting high public expectations of nature action and demand for an Environmental Rights Bill (with rights of access to nature) in their Nature 2030 report.⁶⁶

A handful of other organisations also submitted written responses between April and June 2023, including the [Earth Trust](#), [The Food, Farming & Countryside Commission](#), the [British Trust for Ornithology](#), the [Church of England](#), and the [Scottish Wildlife Trust](#).

Wider public action motivated by the People's Plan is harder to gauge. However, it received significant news and media coverage at the time.⁶⁷ The BBC's *Wild Isles* TV series also received 12 million views per episode; and 70% of viewers surveyed reported considering taking action for nature.⁵¹

2.2.2 Building societal capacity to act

// A really exciting thing for me about observing the final Assembly was that it looked and felt different to other environmental conferences. The energy in the room was amazing. It felt like a really good opportunity to ‘break out’ for the environmental sector.”

Ellen Bradley, Co-Director, UK Youth for Nature, People’s Assembly for Nature Observer

Strengthening expertise and knowledge – and improving capacity and resources for engaging in nature renewal by non-state actors (i.e., citizens, eNGOs, businesses and local communities) – was one of the areas where the impact of the People’s Plan process has been strongest. A significant achievement was creating what felt like a rare moment of convergence for parts of the conservation sector, and an opportunity to relaunch as a united front. This was notable given the challenges the commissioning team reported having faced in bringing even parts of their own organisations together. At the same time, there remained a view from some within the sector that the People’s Plan had been an expensive marketing exercise or felt the money could have been spent more wisely at the community level.

As part of their commitment to deliver on the People’s Plan’s community-centred Calls to Action, the commissioning organisations jointly launched two related campaigns to build further legacy from the initiative, drawing on partnerships with business.

The [Save Our Wild Isles Community Fund](#) raised £2.5m for local communities to act for nature via a crowdfunding initiative led by WWF and RSPB, with support from Aviva. Over 90% of those who took part said projects had made a difference to nature in their local area; over 80% felt more involved in their local community, and 97% believed their work would continue.⁶⁸

[Nature Neighbourhoods](#) provides up to £25,000 in funding to 18 community groups in diverse neighbourhoods across the UK, with the aim of developing community leaders and supporting neighbourhood-level plans for nature and climate action. This has been a two-year collaboration between the three commissioning organisations, funded by the National Lottery Climate Action Fund and Co-op (2023-5).

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2.2 Changes in society: NGOs/charities, businesses and publics continued

The quote from Rory Crawford (Lead for Nature Neighbourhoods, and member of the People's Plan's commissioning team), explains the impact the People's Plan process has had on him, as well as the way Nature Neighbourhoods is implementing the Plan's philosophy to empower communities to engage with nature restoration. Early impacts from the programme are encouraging, with significant positive feedback from participants, who have been supported through an active partnership-building programme offering training in co-design, fundraising communications, and navigating working with local authorities (see the quote from the Zebra Collective who participated in the project, and Box 1 in Section 4 for an overview).

“ The People's Plan for Nature was personally, massively transformational. We have also been able to follow the philosophy of the project in Nature Neighbourhoods, which is about community power, leaning into their agency, listening to them. And for them, not us, to set the agenda. So, for me, that's really fulfilling.”

Rory Crawford,
Nature Neighbourhoods Lead, Member of People's Plan's commissioning team

“ It cannot be overstated how beneficial it is to connect with so many vibrant projects across the UK. We have shared learning and experience that is invaluable to us. Allowing space and time for the network to connect is excellent. The connections being made are important for the growth of the sector.”

Debbie Freeman,
Zebra Collective (Plymouth), Nature Neighbourhoods participant

The People's Plan was also widely perceived by insiders and outsiders of the process to have landed well with the business community, and spurred their sustainability campaigns. The *Save Our Wild Isles* Partnership Business Advocacy Campaign had supported 220 organisations to host business film screenings to promote engagement and encourage change at senior level, and embed nature targets in transition plans (relating to the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures). The films reached 45,000 employees at companies such as Nestle, Pepsi Co, Aviva, PWC, M&S, Premier League, OVO, University of Cambridge, Cross Country Trains and Blackrock.⁵⁴ The initiative's [Nature's Workforce](#) also provided guidance to support employees in starting conversations about nature into their workplaces, whilst the People's Plan website provided [guidance and tools](#) for members of the public to engage their communities and local authorities in restoring nature locally.

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2.2.3 New ways of understanding societal action for nature

// The People's Plan for Nature has been an inspiration to other actors elsewhere. Part of the reason that [the forthcoming Norwegian citizens' assembly] exists is because the People's Plan for Nature showed that civil society organisations could actually do this kind of work."

Professor Graham Smith, *Chair of the Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies*

There is considerable evidence that the People's Plan has impacted on the way action for nature is understood by Assembly members, the commissioning team, and other civil society groups. Assembly members report gaining a deeper understanding about the need and means to act for nature, as well as greater commitment among the commissioners to engage citizens in their work. There have also been spillovers of a deliberative and participatory mindset into parts of the commissioning eNGOs (including leadership, in some cases), and a greater desire to involve the public in decision-making. This is exemplified by the WWF, who have been more closely engaging citizens in their advocacy work, and in the RSPB's commitment to use People's Panels in future nature campaigns. At the National Trust, a participatory approach was used to

engage over 3,700 members of the public in developing its [10-year strategy](#), which puts people, nature and working in partnerships at the heart of its new approach. They have also been exploring holding a citizens' assembly on culture and heritage, and there are hopes that the Nature Neighbourhoods project will provide confidence and proof of concept that the conservation sector is willing and able to put their knowledge and resources in service of empowering local communities to restore nature or more broadly to make their places better.

// I've certainly changed my thinking around the value and purpose of deliberative processes as a result of being so directly involved in this process. Seeing it in action has meant it is something I now advocate for internally and externally in a number of ways. And it is something that is now present in conversations internally in a way that wasn't before."

Member of the People's Plan's commissioning team

2.2 Changes in society: NGOs/charities, businesses and publics continued

The People's Plan has also been an inspiration to actors in the UK and elsewhere. In the UK, the Food, Farming and Countryside Commission (FFCC) is leading [The Food Conversation](#) to engage hundreds of citizens in locally-organised workshops to consider the future of food, in response to the Plan's call for a national conversation about food and nature; and the [Oxford Nature Conversation](#) are citizens' juries being conducted in 2025 to explore local implementation of People's Plan's recommendations.

In addition, the process has inspired citizens' assemblies elsewhere in the world, as well as in other sectors. For example, in Norway, a consortium of NGOs led by [SoCentral](#) is undertaking [Fremtidspanelet](#) ('The Future Panel'), a national assembly responding to the question, "How can we use our wealth to benefit the world, ourselves and future generations?" (with inputs from the People's Plan commissioning team, one of whom sits on their Deliberative Advisory Group).⁶⁹ The International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) drew on the People's Plan approach when developing their citizens' assembly to inform policy on synthetic biology in relation to nature conservation ([Resolution 123](#)).⁷⁰ Members of the People's Plan commissioning team have also been invited to sit on the advisory board for a citizens' assembly led by RSPCA on the future of animal welfare ([Animal Futures: The Big Conversation](#)), which is also applying the RAPID Democracy framework.

2.3 New principles, systems and structures for acting for nature

Experts in public deliberation have talked about the need for citizens' assemblies to be 'system-disrupting' rather than 'system-supporting'.⁷¹ The People's Plan rose to this challenge by creating space to propose notably ambitious and progressive changes to the foundational principles and goals underpinning our governance systems. It called for better integration of nature considerations within UK legal frameworks and policymaking across sectors, and stronger enforcement and tightening of existing regulations. As many of these proposals, if implemented, would span all three 'types of impacts' (ways of doing things, capacity to act, and ways of thinking about nature action), we have merged the three in our analysis here (and in Table 2 below).

Overall, the People's Plan's Calls to Action demonstrated innovative, long-term and holistic thinking to a degree rarely achieved by politicians, corporations or indeed, the nature conservation sector itself. It has been noted that mini-publics run by civil society organisations are often better placed to create this space for a broader systems-thinking approach than government-run processes, which rarely have the freedom or remit to do so. Examples of changes proposed by the People's Plan include: calls for government and companies to take a more joined-up approach to mitigating environmental impacts (in particular, across food, farming and environmental management), enforcement of the 'polluter pays' principle, equitable access to nature as a human right, a Rights of Nature perspective (i.e., giving natural entities the same legal protection as people and corporations), and exploration of the concept of a 'crime against nature' (also known as 'ecocide'). There were also demands for a permanent Assembly for Nature (involving NGOs, industry and public members), and cross-party commitment to a UK Future Well-being Act, along the lines of the Welsh [Well-being of Future Generations Act \(2015\)](#), which legally obliges public bodies to collaborate to achieve economic, social, environmental and cultural wellbeing for the nation. More specific to the business sector, the Plan advocated all corporate boards have a Director for Nature (more on this in [Section 4.5](#)).

2.3 New principles, systems and structures for acting for nature continued

There has perhaps unsurprisingly been limited progress on achieving these objectives, which would require a major recalibration of governance values and overhaul of the UK's legal systems. But changing the societal and political landscape on this scale is a long-term endeavour, and ultimately, work in progress. There have been some small steps forward recently, which future efforts to implement recommendations could build on. For example, a Member of the Scottish Parliament has been consulting on introducing a [Proposed Ecocide Prevention Bill](#), and the number of companies with Future Generations and [Nature On The Board](#) is growing apace (with the [House of Hackney](#) a recent newcomer after [Faith in Nature](#) became the first in 2022) (see [Section 4.5](#) for more details).

There has also been evidence of more joined-up thinking, which relates to the People's Plan's calls for greater leadership and coordination for nature action. Here there has been some progress in land management (including the Environmental Land Management Schemes, the Welsh Agricultural Bill), and also in the development of institutions to support more holistic thinking. This includes the newly established advisory group to the Scottish Government, the [First Minister's Environment Council](#) (which hosts experts in climate and nature), and appointment of the first [Special Representative for Nature](#) to tackle nature and climate change, reporting to the Environment and Foreign Secretaries.

Furthermore, the significance of the People's Plan in presenting a consensus and public mandate on the need for urgent, cross-sectoral action for nature restoration should not be underestimated. In a political climate often characterised by culture wars and emerging 'greenlash' (backlash against environmental movements and green politics),⁷² citizens' assemblies can helpfully act as a buffer against polarisation,³⁹ and the People's Plan has arguably played a role in this process. Above all, it has shown there is an appetite and sense of urgency among a representative cross-section of the public to take more fundamental action, and in doing so, has moved forward appreciation of 'what is possible and acceptable'.^{33,73}

This perception of the People's Plan representing a pioneering innovation was reflected in one of the exercises carried out during the workshop conducted for this research, where participants were asked to give three words to describe the People's Plan for Nature. As Figure 5 illustrates, the words most commonly cited were, 'inspiring', 'groundbreaking', 'powerful', 'exciting' and 'challenging'.

FIGURE 5: WORD CLOUD: WHICH THREE WORDS WOULD YOU USE TO DESCRIBE THE PEOPLE'S PLAN FOR NATURE?
SOURCE: OUTPUT OF AN EXERCISE CARRIED OUT DURING THE EXCASES PARTICIPATORY WORKSHOP, JULY 2024

AREA of impact ↓	TYPE of impact →		
	A. INSTRUMENTAL <i>What is being 'done'</i>	B. CAPACITY <i>Expertise and resources to act</i>	C. CONCEPTUAL <i>Ways of understanding action for nature</i>
1. PUBLIC SECTOR Impacts on government decision-making <i>Key actors: policymakers, politicians, parliamentarians, civil servants</i>	Referenced by senior policymakers to justify more ambitious nature policies, and public access to nature. Sand eel fishing ban had direct links to <i>Save Our Wild Isles</i> .	Provided a strong public mandate for urgent nature action. Supported coalition-building behind the scenes for a more progressive nature agenda.	Contributed to more joined-up land management, and nature and climate policy. Created momentum for a shift in attitudes about the value of using citizens' assemblies and deliberative democracy.
2. SOCIAL/ CORPORATE Impacts on wider society and public discourse <i>Key actors: members of the public, media, businesses, and third-sector (e.g., charities, NGOs)</i>	'Transformative' for participants involved, motivating pro-nature behaviour change. Follow-up programmes have led to greater cross-sectoral collaboration between the commissioning charities, businesses and local communities.	Promoted civic education and supported empowerment to act for nature by Assembly members, commissioners, instigating charities, businesses, and communities involved in follow-up programmes.	Inspired new local, national and international deliberative initiatives, inside and outside the conservation sector (including those run by civil society organisations).
3. SYSTEMS AND STRUCTURES Impacts on underlying features of practices (including decision-making) that alter the goals or mandates that guide climate action	Pushed the boundaries of what ambitious action for nature might look like by: proposing radical pathway (access to nature as a human right, a permanent Assembly for Nature and Nature Directors in all companies), and introducing progressive ideas (relating to the rights of nature and future generations). Provided validation for deliberative democracy as a concept and practice among influential institutions (large conservation charities, delivery partners, senior policymakers), and citizens.		

TABLE 2: EVALUATION FRAMEWORK FOR CITIZENS' ASSEMBLY IMPACTS

SOURCE: ADAPTED FROM KNOCA'S IMPACT EVALUATION FRAMEWORK FOR CLIMATE ASSEMBLIES³

Thinking about overall impacts, UK Research and Innovation, the national public body that oversees research and innovation funding in the UK, considers both significance and reach.³ *Significance* refers to the importance of impacts, whereas *reach* applies to the distance they travel. Although the People's Plan may not have had considerable reach, where it *has* had impact, this has in many cases been significant. Most notably, the People's Plan represents an iconic and pioneering model of a national citizens' assembly commissioned by civil society organisations, which was – uniquely – embedded within a public broadcasting media campaign, a 'National Conversation' and a RAPID Democracy process, aspiring to bring about systems change.

Whilst direct public policy impacts have been limited, deliberative and participatory practices are doubtless being taken more seriously in many social and political spheres as a direct result of the process. Its most significant impacts have been in the societal sphere, where the influence of conservation charities might anyway be expected to be greatest. It is here that individual impacts have been 'transformative', and there has been greatest evidence of: behavioural change; organisational, business, and community capacity-building; conceptual learning (about how action for nature should be framed and conducted); and deliberative spillovers, with the People's Plan demonstrating a model that has inspired other organisations (especially civil society organisations) to follow suit, both in the UK and internationally, across a variety of sectors.

Lessons from the People's Plan for Nature process

3. Lessons from the People's Plan for Nature process

// Where I feel we could have got further: we needed to think about how we might have been able to bring more people along with us."

Member of the People's Plan's commissioning team

Here we explore ten lessons from the People's Plan process, which can also be useful when considering, designing or analysing other deliberative processes (summarised in Figure 6).

KEY LESSONS FROM THE PEOPLE'S PLAN FOR NATURE

- 1 Use an impact strategy and theory of change
- 2 Clearly communicate objectives and limitations
- 3 Engage in co-design to share the journey
- 4 Acknowledge the role of politics and power
- 5 Incorporate equality, diversity and inclusion at every stage
- 6 Demonstrate the integrity and value of the process
- 7 Highlight the importance of leadership buy-in
- 8 Connect deliberative and representative democracy
- 9 Co-deliver and collaborate to maximise reach
- 10 Take a cross-sectoral approach

FIGURE 6: SUMMARY OF LESSONS FROM THE PEOPLE'S PLAN FOR NATURE FOR DELIBERATIVE PROCESSES

Study nature,
Love nature.

3.1 Use an impact strategy and theory of change

// As a sector we don't have a shared theory of change and the role in which citizens play within that theory of change... We tend to set ourselves quite linear project plans, so there is some work to be done in looking at how change happens."

Member of the People's Plan's commissioning team

There is considerable freedom and power in the agenda-setting function for civil society-run, deliberative processes to create spaces for systems-thinking and an opportunity to introduce more complex and 'systems-disrupting' ideas into the public debate. This was demonstrated by the Plan's aspirations to consider 'whole-system change', and its coverage of progressive – even radical – topics. Other non-state actors have called for or followed suit by taking a systems approach in framing their deliberative process agendas, such as [Earth4All](#) and Fairtrans, the latter being a university-led research project, which rolled out a [workshop-based tool](#) as part of the [first national climate assembly in Sweden \(2024\)](#) to support public understanding of the underlying causes and consequences of climate change.^{74,75}

Having a high level of ambition, however, also carries a greater degree of risk, both in terms of whether and how such aspirations will be achievable from a single deliberative event, and how to plan for – and evaluate – their success. In the case of the People's Plan, changing leadership and objectives within the *Save Our Wild Isles* programme, and the absence of an impact strategy and longer-term theory of change, were mentioned by the core team as having been important limiting factors and a 'missing middle' connecting the process to its goals (or 'Perform' function). It was felt that having to take a more reactive approach compromised the team's ability to mobilise the Plan's civic mandate and capitalise on the high point generated by the Attenborough film in their political campaigning and business advocacy work, and to plan for the citizens' onward journeys.

Given that citizens' assemblies operate within the systems they are trying to change, they are also limited in what they can achieve. There is invariably a trade-off between giving citizens free rein in terms of setting policy (as the People's Plan process did to a relatively high degree), and creating a well-informed and implementable policy agenda with government take-up in mind. As a participant closely involved in the process explained, 'It's quite a difficult ask of the citizens to get across the scale of issue, and the geographical differences that exist between different [four nations'] jurisdictions' (Member of the People's Plan's commissioning team).

There was also open acknowledgment by the instigators that they were learning on the job in running one of the first charity-run, national assemblies of its kind. It was not entirely clear what an impact strategy might look like for an NGO-commissioned assembly, bearing in mind it would look very different to a more traditional, state-run citizens' assembly. **The need for an impact strategy and theory of change would therefore be the first lesson to come out of the People's Plan process**, which also echoes KNOCA's recent guidance for civil society-run processes.⁷⁶ As an interviewee outside the process expressed, 'A citizens' assembly can't happen once, and then last forever. You've got to have a programme that then helps it come to life afterwards.' Although the RAPID Democracy framework had been in place from the outset, the attention paid to the 'Perform' stage (i.e., delivering the Plan) had been limited (largely due to reasons out of the organisers' hands). Having a better understanding of how a theory of change could have translated into an impact strategy, and whether/how 'insider' and 'outsider' strategies could coexist (i.e., focusing on government and policy and/or seeking a public mandate and cultural influence),⁵² would therefore have been helpful.

3.2 Clearly communicate objectives and limitations

// “What was different was the scale of ambition, the active effort and consciousness with which we were trying to draw in participants and reach such a different range of audiences.”

Member of People’s Plan’s commissioning team

Citizens’ assemblies are an ‘iconic model’ of deliberative democracy, but they are expensive, time-consuming, and bear a significant opportunity cost. Some participants in the study felt the funds might have been better spent elsewhere, for example, on smaller-scale, deliberative or participatory community activities. A second lesson, therefore, is the **value of being clear about objectives and the level of ambition involved, and effectively communicating what the assembly is trying to achieve**, both internally and externally. This was evidently not entirely transparent to outsiders, some of whom were not aware of the system-change aspirations of the process; others questioned whether a citizens’ assembly was the right tool for the job.

Implicit in this critique was also the need for the commissioning organisations to use their agenda-setting and convening powers more carefully in determining the focus and parameters of the deliberative exercise, which ultimately represented a ‘closed space’.⁷⁷ While deliberative events themselves might be open and transparent, ‘there are still many decisions that happen in closed spaces, particularly regarding the organization and design of the participatory process itself’.⁷⁸ This was true of the People’s Plan’s commissioning phase, where some interviewees felt sidelined, yet called upon to communicate and promote engagement with their memberships after the Calls to Action had been published. We return to this in [Section 4.4](#).

3.3 Engage in co-design to share the journey

// You won't get coverage if people don't follow the story."

Democracy practitioner

Building on the previous lesson, a third message from this study is **not to underestimate the importance of the preparatory stages, and to bring those you want to influence into the process as early as possible – ideally from design to delivery**. This includes agenda-setting, observing, communicating, disseminating, and (ongoing) implementation. The imperative came part and parcel with the philosophy of the New Citizenship Project's RAPID Democracy approach, which promoted the idea of embedding the assembly within a national cultural event (BBC's *Wild Isles* series), and broader 'national conversation'; though in practice, it was unclear whether key messages reached beyond public audiences who were already sympathetic and engaged with the nature cause.

Several commissioning team members mentioned their turnaround had been so tight (squeezed by a delayed sign-off at the start, and transmission of the *Wild Isles* series at the end), that they had less time to engage with business communities, policymakers and community organisations than they would have liked. Relationships and logistics could therefore have been better managed to engage stakeholders earlier in co-design, and to develop a more iterative and adaptive process, building in time to include a wider range of actors and reflect-and-revise based on collective learning along the way. For example, with more planning and resources, it might have been possible to co-create the 'onward journey' with Assembly members, rather than it seeming more like a bolt-on afterthought supported by Groundworks. As the Founder of [All the Elements](#) (a non-profit organisation seeking to increase diversity in the outdoors), explained, without clarity about how her community's voices were being represented or what the specific benefits of being involved might be, it was hard for her community to engage with the process: 'Without that, [my community] were just going to see it as another sector 'thing' that doesn't engage them, that is trying to say that it does, but doesn't really mean anything to them in practice.' At the same time, her own experience of running a session with Groundwork for the People's Plan had been a positive one.

3.4 Acknowledge the role of politics and power

// Impact is not all in design, it is in politics and power.”

Workshop participant

Pervading all of these lessons, is the **need to consider the concept of power**.⁷¹ This is a useful framing for unlocking how longer-term social transformation might occur, and involves asking the question: ‘Will increased engagement...risk simply re-legitimizing the status quo, or will it contribute to transforming patterns of exclusion and social injustice and to challenging power relationships?’⁷⁷ While the People’s Plan has undoubtedly opened new spaces for citizens to act for nature (especially in the societal sphere), and the design of the assembly itself was carefully curated to incorporate diverse representation and facilitated deliberation (with ‘experts on tap, not on top’),³³ underlying political systems and institutions remain key to influencing the significance and reach of current – and potentially future – impacts. As one of the People’s Plan speakers explained a year after the event, ‘there were some really great ideas in there, and my sense was it was a robust and democratic enough process...but my immediate cynicism...is that it won’t go anywhere.’ Indeed, it was only once the Labour Government subsequently came to power (a year after the Plan was published) that more positive impacts began to filter through, largely because its agenda was more aligned with (and amenable to) the People’s Plan’s demands.

Workshop participants pointed out that an ongoing challenge is how to frame ‘system-disrupting’ elements into future theories of change and strategies for deliberative processes. A member of the People’s Plan’s commissioning team admitted that ‘content was more about getting technical information and lived experiences across, and perhaps there was not enough about politics, trade-offs or different methods for achieving change.’ This was echoed by a citizen involved in the process: ‘As Assembly members, we received a lot of information about the nature crisis, but maybe not about the politics’.

3.5 Consider equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI) at every stage

// “We should not expect a single citizens’ assembly to achieve all our EDI expectations. We need to weave in different forms of engagement.”

Professor Graham Smith, *Chair, Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies*

Being an ‘invited space’, **deliberative events provide the opportunity to ‘do EDI better.’**⁷⁷ This begins at the framing stage (e.g., will environmental justice be addressed? Also see [Section 4.5](#)), and follows on through the creation of participant lists, appointing an Advisory Board, inviting speakers, and deciding who should be involved in follow-up, all of which represent opportunities to disrupt existing power biases.⁷⁸

It is important to acknowledge, however, that even the best-intentioned deliberative spaces can be exclusionary, and that **citizens’ assemblies alone are not a panacea** for achieving equality, diversity and inclusion. This is largely because the same patterns of advantage (or disadvantage) that participants hold in society will come into play in deliberative settings, for example, manifesting in the way a participant may appear or communicate.⁴¹

The commissioning team clearly put considerable thought and effort into this aspect of the People’s Plan process, inviting a remarkable variety of [speakers](#), including many with critical perspectives.⁷⁹ Attempts were also made to improve representation when selecting citizens’ assembly members, with additional invitations being sent out in deprived areas (due to poorer response rates), and minority ethnic representation being overweighted to promote fairness and a greater diversity of experiences and thinking. Targets were also set to ensure those who felt less connected to nature were sufficiently included.² In keeping with good practice, Assembly members were paid for their time, travel and subsistence, and care was also taken to accommodate additional support needs (e.g., relating to mobility, childcare, and digital/technical access, and other reasonable adjustments).

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After the Assembly, feedback from participants about their experiences was ‘overwhelmingly positive’, with 89% of participants reporting they found it enjoyable and 87% being proud to have taken part.² Those included in this study were keen to point out how inclusive the atmosphere had been, including for those with protected characteristics (e.g., belonging to marginalised groups, living with physical or mental challenges or being neurodivergent). Yet, there remained perceptions from some people who were peripheral to or outside the process that it could have been made more inclusive for them. For example, some of those who were asked to participate from the conservation sector did not feel they were invited early enough in the process to engage in co-design on their own terms. The process was also seen by some interviewees as being too focused on policy outcomes. Another felt not enough had been done to represent or demonstrate the benefits to minoritised communities: ‘Why would my community interact with the People’s Plan? What is being done to make them feel like it’s representative of them, and that they are part of it?’⁴⁰

Framing the Assembly process within the *Save Our Wild Isles* campaign was also viewed as reinforcing a discredited status quo, ‘You can’t have inclusion in any meaningful way, just because you might have Black and Brown bodies in the room, if you’re already concerned about disrupting the power dynamic, particularly when you have something that is quite white, middle-class, mainstream, BBC-led, and Attenborough-led’ (Dr Ria Poole, EDI practitioner and academic). An Assembly member also pointed out that more work could have been done to translate the Plan into a more accessible format; for example, simplifying language for different audiences and people with additional learning needs. We return to some of these issues in [Section 4.5](#).

“ Implementing the People’s Plan for Nature should be about us doing things in a different way, because otherwise we’ve missed the actual lesson from it.”

Member of the People’s Plan’s commissioning team

3.6 Demonstrate the integrity and value of the process

// For participatory policy making to be successful, we need to demonstrate the rigour and value of the processes.”

Demos, *Cross-party think tank, 2024*⁵

As outlined earlier, in order to maintain accountability and transparency, the People’s Plan used experienced, independent delivery partners (who have also run state-commissioned assemblies). They also appointed an [Advisory Group](#), who ‘were representative of a broad range of ideological standpoints, representing different parts of society, including business, government representatives, academia, NGOs and civil society groups.’⁸⁰ Overall, by adhering to best practice industry standards, and generating a wide range of valuable impacts (see Section 2), the process is widely viewed among democracy experts and practitioners as demonstrating a high degree of integrity. Nevertheless, there have been questions of bias, with concerns raised from both the right and left of the political spectrum.

Some policymakers and a small cohort of Assembly members represented in this study, felt the process could not claim to be impartial when it had been commissioned by three environmental NGOs. Questions were also raised, on the one hand, about why more businesses and farmers had not been invited to speak; and on the other, as to why more radical groups, such as Extinction Rebellion (XR), were not represented as speakers. This was in part owing to the conscious efforts of the commissioning team not to alienate the more conservative or mainstream actors they were seeking to influence (such as farming community and policymakers). It was also pointed out that additional food retail, farming and green finance perspectives were brought in towards the latter stages of the event at the request of citizens (demonstrating the need and value of taking a citizen-responsive approach). XR were only represented indirectly by the Assembly members who happened to belong to the campaigning eco-socialist movement.

Nevertheless, **there remains work to be done to address perceptions that civil society-run assemblies are less credible than state-run events**, and to demonstrate the value of citizens’ assemblies among wider publics, particularly right-leaning members.³³ As a democracy expert pointed out, ‘If you’re right-of-centre, you are less likely to support this form of policy making, and so you’re less likely to volunteer. And if you do, you’re more likely to be dissatisfied with the process, and we’ve got good evidence for that...people have differing views on civic engagement, which in turn affects their interaction with these processes’ (Professor Rebecca Willis). This was confirmed in an interview with an Assembly member who had a history of voting for right-of-centre political parties: ‘We only got one side of the story. Where was the single mother who’s saying, ‘I am more interested in how I am going to pay for the next bit of food than worrying about beetles?’ These people certainly exist because if they didn’t, we wouldn’t have a biodiversity problem. More effort could have been made to find that counter argument’. Although the member did point out he was part of a very small minority of Assembly members holding this position, this speaks to the wider societal challenge of raising public consciousness about the value and legitimacy of deliberative approaches, which would help to improve the diversity of those willing to participate and, in turn, further legitimise such processes.

3.7 Highlight the importance of leadership buy-in

“ Elements of deliberative thinking are coming into our strategic thinking, and a desire for more citizen-led, citizen-engaged and citizen-empowered action. A mindset change is beginning, which I can’t put down purely to [the People’s Plan for Nature], but I think it is assistive of us having done this. It’s an accelerant.”

Member of the People’s Plan’s commissioning team

A mini-public’s level of impact is also a function of how much institutional buy-in there is with the process, and this applies as much to an eNGO-run initiative as to a government-led one. In the case of the People’s Plan, a key lesson has been that **building coalitions within organisations takes time and relies on the support and goodwill of strategic allies, including within the initiating organisations and their senior leadership teams.**

Experiences of how the People’s Plan has been supported and championed by management within the commissioning organisations have been mixed and are still evolving. There has certainly been an appetite to capitalise on the public mandate for pursuing the nature cause, as well as support for more participatory and citizen-led practices at strategic level in some cases. To a degree, this was because the process played into changes that were already underway, but there was also a perception that the People’s Plan provided validation and justification for taking more progressive and inclusive pathways. At the same time, some participants were left with a feeling that opportunities for deeper learning about the need to listen to and empower citizens had been missed.

“ Having gone through a transformation and seeing the value of hearing from a cross-section of society, it felt we were missing the big lesson: what does it mean to actively listen to people, and to bring people into the conversation, to support them, to lean into their agency?”

Member of the People’s Plan’s commissioning team

Unsplash - Lukasz Wojcik

3.8 Connect deliberative and representative democracy

// As an advocacy professional, what I would say is that commissioning [a citizens' assembly] by NGOs meant we didn't have that immediacy of connection into government and decision-makers...we had to create a whole advocacy operation just getting [the Plan] in front of people and getting them to take it seriously."

Member of the People's Plan's commissioning team

Policy impacts are more likely to occur if public policymakers are brought as close to a deliberative process as possible. This helps them to understand its value, bear witness to the integrity of the process, and experience the transformative change often undergone by those involved. This was mentioned by several participants in this project as being a key challenge for the People's Plan, owing to the Assembly being instigated by conservation organisations rather than being embedded within a public process. Although government-run assemblies often fall short of expectations when it comes to delivering policy change (and fall prey to the same political bargaining afterwards), they are more likely to be conferred greater legitimacy in many formal policy and public circles. **Finding better ways to integrate representative and deliberative democracy** was therefore seen as a way of improving the Plan's public policy uptake, as one of the project's participants advocated, 'Include policy-makers within the process throughout so they can understand the issues and be able to ask questions – this is helpful for buy-in later when actions need to be taken' (Dr Ria Poole, EDI practitioner and academic).

Another participant pointed out that citizens' assemblies taking a more bottom-up pathway, can also be seen more positively, as a way to redirect power away from formal public institutions, circumvent elected representatives' waning legitimacy, and embed deliberative democracy by building individual and societal efficacy,⁸¹ which was in many ways a key strength of the People's Plan process.

3.9 Co-deliver and collaborate to maximise reach

// If we just were a little bit less territorial as a sector when we go out and work on these things...I feel we could have got further."

Member of the People's Plan's commissioning team

The unique experiment of the three eNGOs collaborating in the People's Plan also conveyed **the power of each partner playing to their strengths**. For example, with their different memberships, they were able to reach slightly different audiences (the National Trust also reaching a cultural and heritage audience, for example). Individual members of the core team also brought different expertise to the commissioning team, such as expertise in strategy, communications and advocacy.

This unusual collaborative effort also created capacity-building opportunities within the commissioning organisations and delivery partners in the process of organising the deliberative event, and in the follow-up. Indeed, the planning and aftermath were shown to be as important for building coalitions as the Assembly itself, and some of the personal and institutional relationships built across the organisations have outlived the assembly process. Even where senior staff have since moved into new roles within different organisations in the sector, they have retained their entrepreneurial zeal to amplify the Plan's Calls for Action and advocate for deliberative democracy.

In spite of this positive collaborative trajectory, there was certainly scope to have built stronger coalitions across the nature sector as a whole to maximise impacts. It is also notable that the three organisations progressed their political and advocacy campaigning independently of the *Save Our Wild Isles* and People's Plan processes, which may also have been a limiting factor. However, they did join forces in the run up to the 2024 General Election to support the [Restore Nature Now](#) march and [Nature 2030](#) campaign, which demanded 'radical new commitments' and a five-point plan for nature from politicians.⁸²

3.10 Take a cross-sectoral approach

// Some businesses were far more interested [in the People's Plan] than other nature charities."

Member of the People's Plan's commissioning team

In keeping with the spirit of a 'systems' approach to deliberative democracy, which understands democratic environmental governance as a web of interconnected deliberative 'nodes', it is necessary to see not only the nature sector, but all sectors, as being able to contribute and feed into the deliberative conversation about nature – in parallel, sequentially or simultaneously via innovative deliberative and participatory structures. Some participants in this study felt an important lesson from the People's Plan was **demonstrating the value of integrating stakeholders from outside the conservation sector**. One member of the commissioning team was particularly keen to emphasise that, in their view, interventions from businesses to invest more (money and volunteers) in communities as part of the follow-up to the People's Plan process (e.g., the Coop and Aviva's in grassroots legacy projects) represented a more fundamental strength of the People's Plan than direct policy impacts had done.

Recommendations for moving forward together to democratise nature

4. Recommendations for moving forward together to democratise nature

// What's the next way of bringing in citizens and continuing the conversation? These things are never a single moment in time. They're always an ongoing conversation."

Member of the People's Plan's commissioning team

To be successful as a civic mandate, deliberative events such as citizens' assemblies need to signify more than a moment in time, and instead represent a vehicle for more fundamental change. Looking ahead, how can organisations interested or engaged in nature restoration build on the deliberative-democratic aspirations and Calls to Action of the People's Plan?

The following section draws on the personal insights and perspectives of the diverse participants in this study – and touches on the deliberative democracy literature – to present ten recommendations. These highlight some of the barriers participants see to embedding deliberative democracy, and spotlight innovative tools and processes being used on the ground to inspire positive, collective pathways forward.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR BUILDING DELIBERATIVE DEMOCRACY IN THE NATURE SECTOR – AND BEYOND

- 1 Take a holistic 'systems' approach to restoring nature
- 2 Acknowledge and navigate disagreement and conflict
- 3 Place communities at the heart of decision-making
- 4 Cultivate a mindset of power with citizens
- 5 Centre marginalised and unheard voices
- 6 Engage publics and stakeholders in hybrid deliberative processes
- 7 Lead and collaborate across the nature sector – and beyond
- 8 Build an evidence base of public engagement and deliberative initiatives
- 9 Take a 'people and nature' approach
- 10 Recognise transformative change takes commitment, resources and time

FIGURE 7: SUMMARY OF RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Take a holistic 'systems' approach to restoring nature

A first recommendation is that organisations involved or interested in restoring nature take a more **holistic or 'systems' approach to including publics, stakeholders and deliberative democracy** in their work. The idea of a deliberative 'system' can be understood as an ecosystem of labour which takes place across *all* formal and informal decision-making spaces and reaches well beyond specific deliberative events (such as citizens' assemblies and juries).^{37,47}

To apply this approach, active consideration needs to be given to how deliberative campaigns and democratic aspirations align with existing constellations of decision-making processes, within *and* between organisations, businesses, public authorities and publics. By more consciously understanding and building links between deliberative events and governance systems (over time and across locations), it may be possible to help establish the dynamic connections necessary to forge 'ecologies of participation', and embed deliberative values so they become uncontested and instinctive ways of working.^{29,83,84} Often, however, participatory and deliberative processes are used as an ad hoc input, where there is limited clarity about how this will feed into subsequent decision-making, let alone impact environmental governance more broadly.

Permanent, ongoing or rolling deliberative structures, such as citizens' panels, councils or juries can be helpful ways of embedding deliberation into everyday decision-making (see [Section 4.6](#)). These could even be enforced by creating requirements for civil society organisations, businesses or public authorities to carry out deliberative processes under certain

“ We would know [deliberative democracy] was working if we saw the idea was being taken up at every level of decision making. That's a virtuous circle: where people start to expect it because they understand it is the best way we can make decisions - at board level, department level, organisational level, at local authority level. And then we'd reproduce that because we'd understand it's the best practice we've got.”

Tom Lord, *Sortition Foundation*

“ Looking at links between deliberative processes, and **listening** to inform mobilising and organising, could be very powerful, and could help connect outsider and insider campaigning more.”

Member of the People's Plan for Nature's commissioning team

circumstances or by citizens/employees being given the right to demand that a public or private body organise a deliberative process (for example, by having a nature director on their board, see [Section 4.5](#)).²⁹ Establishing a permanent Assembly for Nature, with representation from eNGOs, industry and citizens – as advocated by the People's Plan – would undoubtedly be a powerful way of coordinating deliberative decision-making across sectors.

4.2 Acknowledge and navigate disagreement and conflict

A second important pathway forward involves **viewing deliberative democracy as a valuable means for dealing with conflict and trade-offs**. To be effective, however, deliberative approaches need to be coupled with an appetite for change from those in positions of authority.

The conservation sector has long wrangled with difficult legacies, and without addressing some of these more directly, many marginalised groups will continue to find it problematic – and even painful – to engage with mainstream organisations, who in turn, will remain open to accusations of reinforcing hegemonic, entrenched or patriarchal perspectives.²² Whilst this may in some cases be unintentional, it can nonetheless undermine not only the EDI credibility of such organisations, but also the effectiveness of their conservation programmes, and environmental justice within society at large.

To 'embed' or 'systematise' deliberative democracy, several research participants felt we needed to 'disrupt' existing patterns of exclusivity and create physical and emotional space for more diverse voices. This demonstrates again that deliberative democracy is not only a normative goal, but also a process, and that deliberative fora can be useful for diffusing tensions and providing safer and more productive spaces to discuss and reach understandings about difficult topics and trade-offs. [Sections 4.5](#) and [4.6](#) give examples of how deliberative spaces can be designed to achieve this in practice.

“ If you want to listen well, and you want to be inclusive, you're going to have to include even those who you find most challenging. Otherwise, it's meaningless.”

Dr Ria Poole, EDI practitioner and academic

4.3 Place communities at the heart of decision-making

“ When we asked minorities what they wanted, they wanted things like: grow vegetables, they wanted to have a community garden and so on. And the [environment movement] laughed; they said, ‘well this is not wildlife’, you know. There’s still a big resistance towards this to recognise the process of participation, which is you start where people are. [...] So why do you just bang on about wildness, which is more remote?”

Judy Ling Wong, *Black Environment Network, 2023*⁸⁵

Maintaining a sense of meaning for people in places undergoing change is important. How people’s stories and sense of place are layered onto the histories and cultures of their communities and landscapes will ultimately define whether and how they engage with nature. Judy Ling Wong, who was recently interviewed for a [RENEW/British Library Oral Histories](#) project about her experiences as part of the [Black Environment Network](#), highlights how minority ethnic groups have been calling for **community priorities to be placed at the heart of environmental practices** since the 1980s.⁸⁵ Yet there’s a shared sense that calls to action of this sort continue to be overlooked – something echoed by several participants interviewed for this study.

Although there have been many genuinely innovative and inspiring initiatives seeking to facilitate and promote community-centred approaches (such as [Future Parks Accelerator](#), [Nextdoor Nature](#), [Nature Neighbourhoods](#)), they have so far tended to operate more as collections of pilot projects in urban areas, rather than a way of operating across environmental organisations (the Wildlife Trusts have started to address this through Nextdoor Nature). And while the sector is beginning to gain momentum to act more collaboratively in this area, for example, through [Nature Towns and Cities](#) (a cross-sectoral coalition of organisations working to improve urban green spaces with local communities), there remains significant work to be done to bring this approach into the heart of organisations across their full range of operations.

As illustrated in Box 1, joint projects such as Nature Neighbourhoods are particularly groundbreaking in terms of their endeavour to share risk, forge trust, and provide proof of concept that large eNGOs can work together to support communities in developing their own capabilities to manage local spaces for people and nature. [Nextdoor Nature](#), run by The Wildlife Trusts, is notable for taking a ‘community organising’ approach, which involved placing a dedicated organiser into every Trust and providing them with accredited training. As their Director of Campaigning and Communities, Nikki Williams explained, ‘We’ve spent two years teaching ourselves how to listen to communities as opposed to projecting what we want.’⁸⁶

“ It’s about helping people to work it out for themselves in their own context, in a way that’s relevant to them - that’s what deliberative processes need to do. Then you’re starting to deal with your EDI issues because you’re saying, ‘your context is relevant,’ not ‘this is what I’m going to project onto you.’”

Nikki Williams, *Director of Campaigning and Communities, The Wildlife Trusts*

Spotlight on Innovation 1: Community-centred projects for people and nature

Nature Neighbourhoods

The project was designed as a follow-up to the People's Plan for Nature's community-centred Calls for Action to support the development of neighbourhood action plans for nature and climate. **It is a two-year partnership (2023-5) between National Trust, RSPB and WWF, funded by the National Lottery Climate Action Fund and Co-op.**

Delivering Nature Neighbourhoods has involved:

- Working with 18 community organisations in diverse neighbourhoods across the UK.
- Giving communities ownership of design, development and delivery, and up to £25,000 in funding per neighbourhood.
- Building capacity of diverse local communities by providing development opportunities to 400 community leaders and convening a peer-to-peer support networks.
- Working with Voluntary, Community and Social Enterprise 'anchor' organisations to build capacity of diverse communities.
- Training and empowering system actors at the local level to enable greater capacity for community participation and community-driven actions for nature.
- Building capability of project partners to support community action for climate and nature, improving collaboration at scale.

Nextdoor Nature

The programme aimed to "bring people and communities together to help nature flourish where they lived and worked". **Using a community organising approach, 44 Wildlife Trusts were supported over two years (2022-4), to engage 1,600 communities who were less traditionally likely to access nature in developing nature connection. It was funded by the National Lottery Heritage Fund.**

Actions to deliver the programme included:

- Listening exercises to understand the, "barriers, challenges, needs and wants of communities."
- Building relationships with community groups, associations, schools, and others.
- Developing a package of online/offline information resources.
- Providing training for Wildlife Trust staff and in-person learning.
- Contributing to 'Share Learn Improve' sessions (a reflective process to share problems or successes, and learn from each other to improve collective practice.
- Supporting communities to progress local projects to improve nature outcomes.
- Delivering training to support communities to lead local action for nature (Pioneers Programme, in Scotland only).

BOX 1: SPOTLIGHT ON COMMUNITY-CENTRED PROJECTS RUN BY LARGE CONSERVATION ORGANISATIONS

SOURCES: INTERVIEWS AND DUCIE ET AL. 2024⁸⁶

Another opportunity raised by an interviewee was for organisations to make more use of participatory budgeting as part of their programme design. This is a process of democratic deliberation where publics decide how budgets should be allocated, which has been widely used in Europe and Brazil.^{87,88}

“ We’d love to see participatory budgeting as part of our programme design, especially where communities are involved in the implementation or are the beneficiaries of the funding.”

Member of the People’s Plan’s commissioning team

4.4 Cultivate a mindset of power *with* citizens

Experts on deliberative democracy have increasingly pointed to **the need to ‘normalise’ citizens’ voices being taken seriously in decision-making**. As a democracy practitioner highlighted, ‘institutionalisation of deliberative processes is important. If the public has more of an expectation of this form of decision-making process, and expects outcomes to be taken seriously, it will have greater impact.’ However, acknowledging that politics and power represent challenges and structural limitations is also critical. Many participants in this research called for decision-makers to move away from a mindset of ‘power over’ citizens towards a viewpoint of ‘power with’. This demands a shift away from reliance on opinion polls, focus groups and consultations, to engaging publics in ongoing coconstitutive processes that transform publics and decision-makers alike. As a workshop participant explained, this requires awareness-raising about the value of participatory initiatives in contrast to taking more transactional, campaigning approaches.

“ Unbottling the genie of citizenship means a whole change of power relations. And it is very difficult for the sector to reset itself.”

Member of the People’s Plan for Nature’s commissioning team

[Section 3.4](#) introduced the need for greater power literacy (i.e., unpacking the different ways in which power overtly and covertly shapes biodiversity governance), which may involve considering hidden biases and exclusions, questioning whose knowledge ‘counts’, and creating new spaces to incorporate a wider diversity of voices and viewpoints.^{78,81}

Gaventa’s, ‘[Power Cube](#)’, shown in Box 2 is a useful tool for undertaking power analysis and increasing power literacy.⁷⁷ It demonstrates the explicit and implicit power play in different formal and informal spaces, settings, and structures, and how these dynamics underpin the way people see themselves, what they value, and the meanings they apply to the world.

“ How do we work with citizens and build power with them rather than using them to further our own power?”

Workshop participant

By becoming mindful that each of these dimensions of power matter for biodiversity renewal, step-by-step – like solving a Rubik’s cube – it is possible to move closer to achieving transformative change. The tool is useful for cultivating power ‘with’ citizens as it moves beyond understanding surface issues and conflicts of interest to explore more subtle ways power can be expressed and addressed. It has been applied to examine power dynamics in stakeholder engagement in various conservation projects (including in the National Trust’s Hatfield Forest), and has been further developed as a Guide for Activists and Changemakers.^{78,89}

Spotlight on Innovation 2: The Power Cube as a tool for social change

SPACES OF POWER

Closed: Decision-making behind closed doors, e.g., government, board rooms

Invited: Spaces accessible by invitation, by right or by non-state actors, e.g., political parties, donors, civil society organisations

Claimed/created: Instigated spaces, e.g., social networks and movements, community organisations, protests, occupations

FORMS OF POWER

Visible: Observable decision-making, formal rules, structures and authorities, e.g. Parliament, AGMs, public media

Hidden: Agenda-setting influence to put issues on (or off) the table, e.g., lobbying, advocacy, social media, private networks

Invisible: Beliefs about what is acceptable; socialisation can perpetuate exclusion/inequality, e.g., capitalism, patriarchy, rights of nature

LEVELS OF POWER

Local: Local authorities, community groups and eNGOs

National: National and devolved governments, businesses/farming, third sector, civil society organisations

Global: International fora and networks, e.g., Convention on Biological Diversity, IUCN, Business for Nature, Global Nature Fund

LINKING SPACES, FORMS AND LEVELS OF POWER

Like solving a Rubik's cube

// Transformative, fundamental change happens...in those rare moments when social movements or social actors are able to work effectively across each of the dimensions simultaneously."

BOX 2: SPOTLIGHT ON POWER ANALYSIS: THE POWER CUBE⁷⁷

SOURCE: GAVENTA, 2006⁷⁷

4.5 Centre marginalised and unheard voices

The next recommendation is founded on the idea of environmental justice, which calls for the **meaningful inclusion of all people in environmental governance, ensuring negative impacts do not fall disproportionately on marginalised groups.**^{90–92} It also places a responsibility on the current generation to maintain a healthy environment for this and future generations.

The perspective speaks to concerns that current decision-making about nature often excludes a raft of voices, experiences and interests, notably: people from minoritised ethnic backgrounds, LGBTQIA+ individuals, young people, people living with disabilities or in poverty, future generations, and nature itself.^{21,93–96} Attention and resources are therefore needed to enhance the deliberative capacities of these individuals in informal deliberative initiatives (such as citizens' assemblies), as well as formal political decision-making spaces (including executive board, government, and community leadership levels).⁴¹ These efforts should be informed by an understanding of intersectionality,⁹⁷ which recognises the added complexity around accessing decision-making spaces for people who are multiply marginalised.

This framing also chimes with recommendations from participants, who advocated creating safe spaces, where groups with protected characteristics can engage in processes designed specifically with their needs and interests in mind. These are sometimes referred to as 'enclave' deliberative processes, affinity groups or 'third spaces'.^{9,98} This involves going beyond 'formal' inclusion⁹⁹ to specifically create better environments for building solidarity, empowerment and political efficacy within marginalised or un-/under-represented groups.¹⁰⁰ The latter point is predicated on a warning not to treat everyone equally if we want them to participate equally because marginalised groups and those with language/information processing difficulties may require extra support prior to and during the event, which should be tailored to their specific needs.⁷⁷ This may involve creating opportunities to build rapport and capacity with other group members in advance or providing targeted mentoring and facilitation during a process, which are examples of 'informal' inclusion.⁹⁹ A range of communication styles could also be incorporated in deliberative contexts, such as storytelling, narratives, testimonies,^{101,102} and [legislative theatre](#).^{103–105}

Examples from the environmental sphere have so far mostly taken the form of assemblies with children and young people, including Ireland's Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss; Ireland's [Youth Assembly on Climate](#), Scotland's Climate Assembly and Children's Parliament, the Copenhagen Youth Climate Assembly, and the (more permanent) [National Youth Assembly of Ireland](#). More recently, an interviewee pointed out that practitioners and civil society organisations have begun scoping assemblies dedicated to people of colour. In the private sector, the Body Shop recruited a [Youth Collective](#) to sit on their board, who represent a range of minority ethnic backgrounds, LGBTQIA+ identities, and other marginalised personal characteristics (and with consideration for the balance of extrovert and introvert members).¹⁰⁶ Members reported this had the positive benefit of acting as a cultural gateway for more diverse thinking under the guise of a 'youth' initiative. For those wishing to involve children and young people in citizens' assemblies, KNOCA have produced comprehensive guidance.¹⁰⁷

“ We are appalled today that in the past it was acceptable for women to be ‘spoken for’ by men in society. One day in the future, I think we will be appalled that we didn’t include nature’s voice - we just decided for nature and didn’t see the inherent bias.”

Brontie Ansell, *Lawyers for Nature*

There is also a considerable body of literature demonstrating that deliberation can support the effective representation of future generations by creating incentives and spaces for longer-term thinking, and opportunities for co-ordinating initiatives across generations.¹⁰⁸ Representing future generations and nature obviously poses additional challenges – but also presents opportunities.¹⁰⁹

Innovative methods are emerging for incorporating ‘unheard voices’ into decision-making. For example, inspired by Iroquois philosophy, [Missions Publiques](#) have been exploring how to apply the ‘[Seventh Generation Principle](#)’, whereby decisions must be made with consideration for the needs and impacts of populations living seven generations ahead. They also join [Moral Imaginations](#) in experimenting with visualisation and meditative techniques. The [Future Design](#) movement have introduced creative intergenerational role play as a model of participatory decision-making in Japanese cities.¹¹⁰ Elsewhere, resources have been developed to support the use of [Council of All Beings](#) rituals, which embody the principles of deep ecology.^{111,112} The Welsh [Wellbeing of Future Generations Act](#) goes a step further by creating a legal obligation for public authorities to consider the long-term impacts of their decisions on social, cultural, environmental and economic wellbeing.

More groundbreaking still, the ‘Rights of Nature’ approach, ‘suggests that Nature, including ecosystems and species, should possess legal rights and the capacity to engage in the legal system through human representatives.’¹¹³ [Lawyers for Nature](#) propose three ways of implementing this approach. First, substantive rights could be given to nature (equivalent to human rights). Second, procedural law could allow nature to be represented as a legal entity, as companies are already. Third, the concept of guardianship could be evoked, encouraging individuals to take on informal or legal guardianship of a specific species or ecosystem (such as a river). This would allow people to advocate for the entity within the existing legal framework (along the lines of parental guardianship), taking on a duty of care and bringing those responsible for harming the entity to account within the existing legal system. This has been demonstrated by the [River Roding Trust](#), which gained charitable status to restore the River Roding for public benefit (see Box 3).

In a corporate context, [Faith in Nature](#) have worked with [Lawyers for Nature](#) and the Earth Law Center to more formally apply the concept of guardianship, giving nature a seat on their executive board by [appointing a Nature Director](#) in 2022.¹¹⁴⁻¹¹⁶ Inspired by this model, [House of Hackney](#) followed suit, extending the scope of the Director’s role to incorporate ‘Mother Nature and Future Generations’ (Box 3). There is considerable scope for other charitable organisations, businesses and even public bodies to follow suit, and eNGOs are in a particularly good position to explore how they could build and support local, regional or national networks of guardians.

Spotlight on Innovation 3: Representing nature and future generations

Nature on the Board: Giving unheard voices a seat at the table

In 2022, *Faith in Nature* became the first company in the world to put 'Nature on the Board'. This involved applying a guardianship model whereby nature's voice was represented by a Director acting for its interests (in this case, a lawyer, followed by Eden Project's Head of Biodiversity). Several companies have since followed suit, and a national park also appointed Nature to their Board of Trustees in 2023.

- These pioneering initiatives define 'Nature' as including human beings (including staff wellbeing). House of Hackney have created a Director for Nature and Future Generations, adopting the Indigenous People's, 'Seventh Generation principle' of decision-making, which incorporates the wellbeing of future humans, plants and animals.
- The legal framework is developed on a bespoke basis for each organisation, but usually gives Nature participatory and representation rights (e.g., voting, agenda-setting), access to a budgets, plus time and resources to conduct research and enlist the help of experts.

Guardianship: The solution to pollution?

The *River Roding Trust* was established in 2019 by a community of boat dwellers, who had begun residing along the previously derelict and litter-choked upper river.

- The group acquired charitable status to: "preserve, protect and restore the River Roding for the public benefit and to undertake and carry on projects and activities of a charitable nature related to the river which will assist in promoting recreation, protecting the environment and educating the public about the history of the river."
- The Trust undertakes a guardianship role to represent the river. It engages the local community in eco-education and activities to clear refuse, monitor water quality and wildlife, plant trees, manage flooding, create paths, and undertake habitat restoration.

BOX 3: USING GUARDIANSHIP TO REPRESENT UNHEARD VOICES

SOURCES: *LAWYERS FOR NATURE, AND THE RIVER RODING TRUST*¹¹⁷

4.6 Engage publics *and* stakeholders in hybrid deliberative processes

New forms of deliberative governance are also starting to emerge which provide opportunities for 'publics' or specific cohorts within a defined population (such as employees, local communities, members, stakeholders) to engage with decision-makers – and each other – in innovative ways. These are sometimes referred to as 'hybrid'¹¹⁸ or bespoke processes because they enact deliberative democratic principles, but implement them in more flexible or partial ways (in contrast to highly formulaic and structured processes like citizens' assemblies, which share certain key characteristics). **Using bespoke participatory and deliberative methods can support environmental decision-making, and have the advantage of being flexible and cost-effective.** They can happen over longer periods of time (e.g. citizens' panels and councils), bring publics and stakeholders together in separate, parallel processes ('hybrid' arrangements) or take place in a shared space (e.g., 'Future Design' introduced in [Section 4.5](#)).^{110,119} The UK public participation charity, [Involve](#), list almost [60 different examples](#), and [New Citizenship Project](#) present a range of tools, which they show can be targeted at different stages of decision-making processes.⁴⁹

In the public sector, mini-publics have been used in creative ways by MPs in Australia to better understand citizens' perspectives about pending political decisions, and the Scottish government have used a citizens' panel to explore minimum income guarantees. Perhaps most comprehensively, in [Erlangen, Germany](#), politicians, NGOs, city-owned companies, civil servants and citizens were all engaged in parallel processes feeding into the development of the city's roadmap for achieving climate neutrality.¹²⁰ In the private sector, an interviewee recounted that a Dutch pension provider has used citizens' assemblies to feed into decision-making on future investments, and an international charity has also used sortition to appoint members of staff to an internal advisory board. Another interviewee pointed to the Coop's [National Members' Council](#), which consists of elected members championing collective and corporate values.

// We need to figure out how to integrate citizen and stakeholder forms of engagement in ways that are complementary."

Workshop participant

“ It really showed that anybody from any background could grasp quite technical information if you gave them time, you explained it to them, and they had the opportunity to question you. And it showed us, where there’s controversy, [deliberative democracy is] really useful to open the discussion. It reframed the question.”

Toni Scarr, *Rethinking Water Lead*,
Environment Agency

©National Trust Images/Chris Lacey

A further interesting initiative, which we feature as a Spotlight on Innovation, is the [Rethinking Water](#) project. This involved a series of citizens’ juries run by the Environment Agency between 2021-2. Despite being standard ‘mini-publics’ to a degree, they stand out as having ‘hybrid’ features due to their explicit multi-sectoral stakeholder involvement in co-design and post-event engagement with outputs. The idea stemmed from a realisation that public bodies often had technical accountability, but lacked local mandates and policy coherence, and that those conventionally involved in consultations were not usually representative of local communities. As Box 4 elaborates, five citizens’ juries were set up around water catchments in different regions of England to generate recommendations and create local visions to support the Agency’s goal of delivering clean air, land and water. The project was designed in collaboration with public, private and eNGO stakeholders, and produced outputs that have been used by communities and the Agency to lobby for change and a more holistic, strategic approach to water management at the local and national levels. As the quote from the Project Lead confirms, the model provided a useful means for engaging the public, rebuilding relationships between stakeholders where they had been tense, and reframing the way water management was perceived and navigated by stakeholders, communities and policymakers.

Spotlight on Innovation 4:

Citizens' juries involving stakeholders in co-design

Rethinking Water

Between 2021-2, the **Environment Agency (EA)** ran parallel online citizens' juries in five different regions of the UK to help prioritise their work towards achieving their 'EA2025' goal of delivering healthy air, land and water. The deliberative process was designed to support a more holistic and locally-mandated approach to managing river catchments, and was structured around the question: *'How do you connect with water in your local environment, and what needs to be changed in the future to benefit people and wildlife?'*

- After trialling youth panels, and working with deliberative democracy experts, the EA appointed local and advisory panels and engaged Involve to carry out **five citizens' juries** around the River Ouseburn (North East), River Wharfe (Yorkshire) and the Thames Valley (Chilterns), River Thames Estuary (South East), and Windermere (Lake District).
- **National and Local Advisor Panels were involved in co-design**, and comprised a range of public, private and third sector organisations. Nationally, these included, RSPB, Yorkshire Rivers Trust, Rivers Trust, Northumbrian Water, National Farmers Union, Salmon and Trout Trust, Ofwat, Natural England, Shellfish Association, Consumer Council for Water, and Universities of Durham, Leeds and West of England. Further groups were engaged locally.
- **Efforts were made to improve the diversity of representation** by recruiting a higher proportion of young people (including 16+), broadening geographical regions to include more deprived urban areas, and where residents from lower indices of deprivation were absent, visitors were included to improve the range of experiences and backgrounds of participants.
- Each of the five juries produced **context-specific recommendations**.
- **Impacts** have included: creating five civic mandates, which local communities have used to **influence** local authorities and water companies, and the EA has used to lobby ministers; improving trust between the EA and participating organisations; strengthening relationships between participating stakeholders; stimulating **local organising, capacity-building** and **engagement with local decision-makers** (and the EA) on strategy and funding.

BOX 4: THE ENVIRONMENT AGENCY'S RETHINKING WATER CITIZENS' JURIES

SOURCES: INTERVIEW AND THE ENVIRONMENT AGENCY¹²¹

4.7 Lead and collaborate across the nature sector – and beyond

// The conservation sector is guilty of replication – how do we sit together as a mosaic?"

Member of the People's Plan commissioning team

The need for leadership and partnerships between organisations acting for nature were recommendations made by the People's Plan,² and were reiterated by several interviewees, in particular, in light of the challenging funding climate and culture wars.

Alongside strategic direction, many felt dedicating time, resources and training was necessary to successfully manage partnerships, deliver deliberative and participatory processes, and integrate lessons into governance structures. Even learning the language of participatory processes was highlighted as being a potential barrier that would need to be overcome (The Wildlife Trusts have consciously worked on this with their leadership teams as part of the Nextdoor Nature project). Others mentioned creating complementary, cross-organisational sets of training and toolkits to support, inspire and empower other organisations, communities and individuals to renew biodiversity would be useful (as Nature Neighbourhoods and Nextdoor Nature have begun to do).

Properly prioritising, managing, resourcing and coordinating deliberative democracy within governance systems applies as much to public authorities and funders as to environmental organisations. The OECD makes clear that 'For institutionalisation to be possible, public authorities should invest to ensure sufficient capacity in the civil service and civil society to commission and deliver representative deliberative processes, as well as sufficient funding.'²⁹

// You need leadership in an organisation to make things like the People's Plan for Nature stick. People don't always have the time to incorporate it into their day-to-day, into that extra 5-10% that you might have on the edge of your desk, which is disappearing for a lot of the sector anyway because of capacity, money and everything else."

Member of the People's Plan team

4.8 Build an evidence base of public engagement and deliberative initiatives

A consolidated effort is needed to build understanding and learning about public engagement and deliberative practices that are already underway in the environmental space. There is significant power and value in creating networks of expertise within – and between – organisations to share and advance knowledge and experience on what works in practice.

This point is exemplified by an ongoing collaborative study between Natural England and the University of East Anglia, which has created a living *Public Engagement Laboratory*. As demonstrated in Box 5, the initiative seeks to: map diverse forms of public engagement (including those not led by institutions); experiment with novel approaches; engage with learning and evaluation; and promote responsiveness and connectivity with governance processes.¹²² The approach is built on the understanding that all publics are: *diverse*, i.e., they have multiple roles (also see [Section 2.2.2](#)); they are *constructed*, which means behaviours are shaped by how publics engage or are engaged (they will behave differently in a citizens' jury than in a public consultation); and (c) they are *systemic*, i.e., our relationships with publics are evolving, and feed into wider systems and 'ecologies of participation'.¹²² This dynamic and connected way of viewing publics, institutions and practices relates back to the idea of a deliberative system.^{6,84}

Spotlight on Innovation 5:

Mapping public engagement with nature and biodiversity

Natural England's Public Engagement Laboratory for Nature and Society is a new way of **applying social science approaches to participation practices within organisational and policy settings**. It has been developed via a partnership between researchers at the *Science, Society and Sustainability (3S) Research Group* at the University of East Anglia and Natural England, and builds on methods used by the , and builds on methods used by the UK Energy Research Centre's Public Engagement Observatory.

KEY AIMS OF THE LABORATORY ARE:

- 1** To **map diverse forms of public engagement** with nature and biodiversity on an ongoing basis and make this evidence openly available;
- 2** To **experiment with novel approaches** to public engagement with nature and biodiversity and translate them into practice;
- 3** To transform **learning and evaluation** through new ways of seeing, connecting, and reflecting on public engagement; and
- 4** To **enhance the responsiveness of governance processes** to diverse public engagements with nature and biodiversity.

These aims are addressed through the four overlapping functions shown in the diagram

BOX 5: THE PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT LABORATORY FOR NATURE AND SOCIETY

SOURCE: CHILVERS ET AL, 2024¹²²

4.9 Take a 'people and nature' approach

// We silo the work that we do. We have human social justice organisations, and then we have niche conservation organisations, and a barrier between the two."

Nadia Shaikh, *Right to Roam*

The nature crisis should be seen as primarily a social challenge. The legacy of historic framings about the purpose of nature conservation as being 'nature for itself', 'nature despite people' and 'nature for people' still casts a long shadow over the sector, creating tensions in objectives, methodologies and metrics of success.¹²³ In recent decades, there has been a shift away from traditional, species- and habitat-centric approaches (focusing on 'wilderness' and 'protection'), towards an emphasis on the dynamic, two-way relationship between 'people and nature' (highlighting ecosystem resilience and sociological systems). However, the outlook and practices of the sector remain inconsistent (sometimes because different nature visions may be valid in different contexts), and often reveal traces of previous visions of nature as 'exclusive' (think nature 'reserves' as per 'Nature for itself') on the one hand or tradeable on the other ('Nature for People' as in carbon offsets or biodiversity net gain). This failure to see people as *part* of nature was powerfully evoked by some interviewees, who felt the sector – and society at large – still had a long way to go to demonstrate a 'people and nature' approach, arguing that habitat fragmentation, pollution, intensive agriculture, and concentrated land ownership, posed considerable challenges to establishing a shared human-nature existence in practice.

// "It's all about societal relevance. When people work out for themselves why nature is relevant, they'll be able to talk about it, advocate for it, take action for it."

Nikki Williams, *Director of Campaigning and Communities, The Wildlife Trusts*

Unsplash - Ava Sol

WE ARE
ONE
WITH
NATURE

Interviewees also raised concerns that the dominance of a natural science perspective in the sector left conservation organisations prone to overlooking the value of social, cultural and emotional experiences.

Members of the [Raven Network](#), an independent support group for ethnically diverse people working across the environment sector, felt there was also work to be done in recognising the experiences of marginalised communities, associated with social exclusion and disconnection with nature. As the Network lead explained, 'I am helping these [ethnically diverse] people working for eNGOs who are really traumatised.'

Acknowledging the emotional labour involved in taking a relational approach (from grassroots to executive level) was seen to be important for bringing about meaningful change. At the leadership level, it was felt there needed to be more appetite to engage with social and environmental justice, greater willingness to build socially just partnerships, and participants pointed to the value of community-led approaches to create greater societal relevance and connection with nature (also see [Sections 4.3](#) and [4.5](#)).

A recent study published by a taskforce of climate experts has also proposed **cultivating better social science literacy to help understand processes of societal change**.¹²⁴ It highlights the need to draw on social science methodologies and evidence, which shows that pursuing fairness in processes and outcomes is fundamental to delivering transitions and policies that have popular support, alongside the need for place-sensitive and people-centred interventions. A corresponding [Nature Recovery Taskforce](#) will be gathering social science expertise this year (until October 2026), to explore how social science can be used to inform land use and management to deliver nature recovery.¹²⁵

“ We read the State of Nature report and analytically identify the problem with nature. Everything is empirical, measured and scientific. But this dissociation from feeling means that we focus too much on ‘problem-solving’ and lose understanding of ‘feelings’ in spaces.”

Member of the Raven Network

Finally, a study looking at the challenges and opportunities for integrating social science research at the Wildfowl and Wetlands Trust (WWT), concluded there is a need for conservation NGOs to: improve their competence in social science theory and methods, incorporate longer-term approaches, and encourage self-reflection to acknowledge the political nature of conservation.¹²⁶

4.10 Recognise transformative change demands commitment, resources and time

// These processes take longer than perhaps NGOs expect. And we're not sure how to support the longer-haul process of change against the institutional challenges of project lifecycles, budgets, etc., and perhaps an impatience to see results happen quicker."

Member of the People's Plan's commissioning team

Unlike elections, where definitive results usually emerge soon after votes have been cast, evaluating the progress and outcomes of deliberative processes, such as a citizens' assemblies, is a more complex and open-ended endeavour. Rather than expecting instantly discernible or causal policy change, it is more likely to be the case that seeds of change are sown, for example, where a deliberative event produces a strong public mandate, this may contribute to progressive action for nature and support 'slow burning' possibilities, rather than trigger instant results. Therefore, **there is a need to keep monitoring and tracking change, and to consider significance and reach, as well as unanticipated impacts.** By embedding reflective evaluation, there will be greater possibilities for ongoing collective learning and awareness of longer-term social change.⁸¹

Furthermore, it is important for citizens' assemblies (and 'mini-publics') not to be seen as the only tool in the box for promoting deliberative democracy. Those commissioning deliberative events also need to commit to the strategic goal of creating spaces for system change within their own organisations and networks, and demonstrate a willingness to empower citizens and stakeholders in a more sustained way. The legacy of citizens' assemblies, such as the People's Plan, need to be seen more in terms of how successful they have been at reclaiming participatory governance and building collective efficacy, than the degree to which they have aligned with or reinforced top-down approaches that may hamper system change in the longer-term.³⁰

This also means that funding streams need to be brought more in line with longer-term thinking. Both Nature Neighbourhoods and Nextdoor Nature aimed to build capacity and generate legacies in local communities to help restore natural environments, but received only two years of funding from the National Lottery Community Fund/Coop and National Lottery Heritage Fund respectively. This is a relatively short length of time to achieve lasting impact, as reflected in the evaluation report of the former (the latter project is still in progress).⁸⁶ Funders therefore also need to be aware of the need to promote legacy by making longer-term finance available to support lasting transformative societal change that will be the bedrock for tackling the nature and climate crises.

Conclusion

5. Conclusion

// Getting a better model of citizen engagement and deliberative democracy going is such an exciting opportunity, and the People's Plan for Nature process has opened that door well."

Richard Benwell, *Wildlife and Countryside Link*

Deliberative democracy is an aspiration and a direction of travel. This study concludes that the People's Plan for Nature can be viewed in much the same way: as a process and a journey on the right track. It has already demonstrated a high level of ambition for system change for nature renewal, and delivered tangible impacts across policy and societal spheres, but there remain challenges and opportunities for embedding deliberative democracy further in the nature sector and beyond.

The project has shown that deliberative initiatives, such as the People's Plan, can play an important role in addressing some of the widely recognised deficits of representative democracy. It argues the case that democratic deliberation provides an alternative and complementary approach by improving the quality, legitimacy, and feasibility of environmental decision-making processes and outcomes.³⁵

In terms of the quality of decision-making, the People's Plan has offered the opportunity to convene citizens and experts in a rapid, yet transformative, exercise in mutual communication and learning, and to unpick why current ways of working are not delivering for nature or people. It has created a facilitated space to collectively produce 26 comprehensive Calls to Action across eight pertinent themes, targeted at a range of actors. By explicitly mitigating power imbalances, and creating new and more transparent spaces to bring diverse voices together, it has equipped and empowered citizens, communities, conservation organisations, businesses and policymakers to advocate and act for nature (as seen in [Section 3](#)). Further, by generating a publicly mandated blueprint for nature action at a time when other public arenas were not open to progressing these issues, the process has performed an important agenda-setting function.

To be legitimate in the longer-term, however, decision-making across the sector and at all levels needs to be made more equal and inclusive. The People's Plan has shown the power and value of more diverse voices being brought to the decision-making table and has provided the opportunity to 'do EDI better'. However, it also raises the question of how a legacy of going 'beyond' inclusion will be maintained outside the best practice 'bubble' of the citizens' assembly model, and how it can be integrated into environmental governance structures more broadly. The study concludes that only by going beyond formal inclusion and embracing creative and diverse communication styles can a wider range of voices be authentically engaged and amplified. This requires creating better environments for building solidarity, empowerment and political efficacy within marginalised and under-represented groups, and finding innovative ways of including unheard voices, such as future generations and nature itself: for example, via guardianship models and appointing directors for nature and future generations to company boards (discussed in [Section 4.5](#) and [Box 3](#)). In addition, those in positions of power need to be willing to ask difficult questions, navigate trade-offs and accommodate those who might not share the same perspectives or lived experiences.

With respect to the feasibility of delivering effective outcomes for people and nature, there are strong indications from participants in this study that a positive legacy has already emerged. Despite its imperfections, the process has undoubtedly promoted civic education, paved the way for more ambitious and joined-up policies for nature restoration, and accelerated a shift in attitudes about the value of citizens' assemblies and deliberative democracy more widely (prompting others to follow suit, in the UK and abroad). The People's Plan has also raised the salience of pro-nature policy and pushed the boundaries of what ambitious action for nature could look like: by proposing radical new pathways such as access to nature as a human right, representation of future generations, a permanent Assembly for Nature, and a Director for Nature on every company board. It has empowered a fresh cohort of citizens, whose deliberative muscles have newly been flexed and whose appetite for change is now matched with a sense of agency about how they might achieve this. Thanks to the People's Plan, there is now a coalition of organisations in the conservation and environment sectors who are more committed to working with citizens, communities and businesses in multi-partner and cross-sector collaborations. Though there remains some way to go before this becomes embedded, it is undoubtedly a substantial step forward. This research has also shown how the People's Plan has heightened the level of awareness, trust and confidence among a significant cohort of decision-makers and societal actors to implement a more nature-positive agenda. Through follow-on projects, communities have been given training, resources and opportunities to develop and realise their own visions of nature and green spaces in their local neighbourhoods.

At the same time, we can see that the uptake of the People's Plan's Calls to Action, and the model of deliberative democracy it advocates, will ultimately depend on the prevailing political climate as the outputs of the process are fed back into the political systems from which they have emerged. In the words of Professor Graham Smith (Chair of the KNOCA network): 'We need to figure out how assemblies can best be embedded with other parts of the political system that themselves may need to be reformed and restructured.'³³

To this end, Figure 8 presents a summary of ten key lessons and recommendations from the People's Plan process (detailed in [Sections 3](#) and [4](#)) to demonstrate how we can collectively build on this legacy to better mainstream the principles of deliberative democracy into broader environmental governance. Pervading these recommendations is the central need to understand how a holistic, deliberative system might work in practice. Findings from this study suggest that this involves creating greater consciousness about who decides for nature; namely, who is included, who is marginalised, and who is missing. Only by casting a more power-critical eye on existing biases in the ways – and places – decision-making systems operate (referred to as 'power literacy' in [Section 4.4](#)), will it be possible to develop innovative and appropriate means of addressing them.

Further, a more normative approach is needed. This means cultivating a mindset of power with citizens, centring marginalised and unheard voices, and taking a community-based and 'people and nature' approach. In turn, this can create opportunities to incorporate environmental justice and embed principles of inclusion and equality. Finally, using more experimental and reflexive methods, including flexible/hybrid deliberations to create safe spaces ('enclaves'), and building an evidence base of where public engagement works best, can provide a stronger justification for deliberative processes being linked to responsive environmental governance (explored in [Sections 4.5](#) and [4.8](#)).

We hope findings from this work offer food for thought, valuable examples of innovation to draw from, and inspiration to adopt more inclusive, deliberative and participatory approaches to deliver the positive outcomes for people and nature we so urgently need.

Summary of lessons and recommendations

Embedding deliberative democracy in the nature sector

Lessons from the People's Plan for Nature	Recommendations for building a holistic deliberative system for nature
1 Use an impact strategy and theory of change	1 Take a holistic 'systems' approach to restoring nature
2 Clearly communicate objectives and limitations	2 Acknowledge and navigate disagreement and conflict
3 Engage in co-design to share the journey	3 Place communities at the heart of decision-making
4 Acknowledge the role of politics and power	4 Cultivate a mindset of power <i>with</i> citizens
5 Consider equality, diversity and inclusion at every stage	5 Centre marginalised and unheard voices
6 Demonstrate the integrity and value of the process	6 Engage publics and stakeholders in hybrid deliberative processes
7 Highlight the importance of leadership buy-in	7 Lead and collaborate across the nature sector – and beyond
8 Connect deliberative and representative democracy	8 Build an evidence base of public engagement and deliberative initiatives
9 Co-deliver and collaborate to maximise reach	9 Take a 'people and nature' approach
10 Take a cross-sectoral approach	10 Recognise transformative change demands commitment, resources and time

FIGURE 8: SUMMARY OF LESSONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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ExCASES Mission

Who decides for nature?

Embedding deliberative democracy in biodiversity renewal

ExCASES is a 'solutions generator' designed to tackle issues facing biodiversity renewal that are not covered by RENEW's four core themes. It provides an agile, flexible mechanism to work collaboratively with partners, researchers, and organisations from diverse sectors on focused topics. This cross-cutting theme is run by an interdisciplinary team of researchers based at the National Trust and the University of Exeter.

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